

A Comprehensive Review of Risk and Threat Taxonomies

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As each new type of event occurs, society reacts retrospectively to recognize the threat and put new safety measures into place, and companies often instigate new risk management techniques specifically for the threat that has just emerged. And yet few of these disruptive events are unprecedented. It is common for risk management approaches to investigate the “emerging risks” or unforeseen perils. Many companies have instituted “emerging risk” monitoring systems, committees, or other processes [4].

Disruptive technologies, geopolitical competition and increasingly demanding regulatory requirements are impacting the cyber and physical threat landscapes. This therefore makes it more and more crucial to adopt a holistic view of how the intertwined global digital ecosystem may impact the security. Fine tuning risk management strategies to survive in the global digital threat landscape is essential. The growing complexity, pace and scale of global interconnectivity and the architecture on which it relies will present organisations with increasing systemic digital threats, some of which are challenging to mitigate.

Such transformative technologies increasingly present macro-level threats that are agnostic of end-users and organisations. Organisations across sectors will therefore have to develop a strategic understanding of the specific risk profiles of each of these technologies. Emerging technologies will also enable devices, networks and services to become hyperconnected and interdependent, and to operate on sophisticated shared infrastructures. This can therefore make it more difficult to identify threats and also the impact of an attack against one component will be increasingly severe. The internet-connected cyber-physical systems that form the basis of Industry 4.0 will become a key focus of criminal actors who will seek to disrupt operational processes to extort significant ransoms. Emerging AI and machine learning-enabled defences, as well as powerful threat intelligence and information-sharing frameworks, can help network defenders to automate security policies, detect threats and support mitigation more broadly. Technology will be a crucial catalyst in responding to emerging technology threats. However, it must be complemented by business leaders’ commitment to adopting a holistic risk management approach, making strategic decisions when developing transformation roadmaps, managing IT and suppliers through governance and controls, and investing in skills and the broader organisational security culture. It is important to have an adequate understanding of the threat landscape, especially due to the fact that the consequences of an attack on any Critical Infrastructure would be dangerous and devastating [5].

In order to have a common guideline, it is fundamental to fix some of the basic concepts that help people to better understand risk deal with prediction, probability versus possibility, precision versus accuracy, and subjectivity versus objectivity. Moreover, several different descriptions of what constitutes the threat, vulnerability, and risk currently exist. Much of the risk profession and the operational risk discipline has not adopted standard definitions for these terms [6].

1.1 Risk Taxonomy

A variety of definitions exist, but the risk management community has not yet adopted a consistent definition for even the most fundamental terms in its vocabulary such as threat, vulnerability, even risk itself. Without a sound common understanding of what risk is, what the factors are that drive risk, and a standard use of the terms used to describe it, risk analysts cannot be effective in delivering meaningful, comparable risk assessment results [7].

Risk Management terms are used with different meanings. Similarly, experts in the area of Risk Management and Risk Assessment use often different definitions for relevant terms. The use of differentiated terminology aggravates the comparability of the achieved results, used methods and tools.

The field currently suffers from confusion of definitions. It is fundamental to provide a foundation vocabulary that summarizes the wide range of terminology in use and proposes a standardization of risk terminology [8].

Building a common understanding of risk management through development of a risk lexicon, risk-informed planning process, training, and standards of practice. The ability to communicate precise concepts and meanings is essential for effective risk-informed decision making. Clear communication allows information to be used

consistently to support decisions about the nature, cause, and severity of risks. This ability to communicate security risk information with precision is critical to support decision making at all levels [9].

Without a logical, tightly defined taxonomy, risk assessment approaches will be significantly impaired by an inability to measure and/or estimate risk factor. This, in turn, means that management will not have the necessary information for making well-informed comparisons and choices, which will lead to inconsistent and often cost-ineffective risk management decisions [7].

The PRECINCT project joined together a multitude of professionals from various areas of CI sectors to cooperate among themselves to collaboratively and efficiently manage security and resilience by sharing data, Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) models and related new resilience services encapsulated in Digital Twins. This cooperation and knowledge sharing between the different partners entailed, inter alia, the building of a common lexicon, to serve as reference for the exchanging of information and expertise; this lexicon is presented here in a taxonomy form that:

- Promulgates a common language to ease and improve communications.
- Facilitates the clear exchange of structured and unstructured data.
- Provide consistency and clear understanding with regard to the usage of terms.

The PRECINCT approach is to provide a common risk taxonomy starting from the current taxonomies, merging them in order to have a full coverage of risk terminology.

A standard definition and taxonomy for information security risk has been provided by The Open Group, namely The Open Group Standard for Risk Taxonomy. This is a general taxonomy that can be applied to any risk scenario as a foundation for normalizing the results of risk analyses across varied risk domains. The taxonomy describes the factors that drive risk along with their definitions and relationships. To further refine risk and its components, a first taxonomy overview but not comprehensive (as deeper layers of abstraction exist that are not shown) is provided in the following Figure 2:

Figure 2: High-level Risk Taxonomy Abstractions

Other taxonomies and sources have been analysed such as ENISA [8], the Cambridge Taxonomy [4], the DHS Risk Lexicon [9], the ISO/IEC Guide 73 and so on. Then, the relevant terms have been gathered in the following Table 1. This Risk Taxonomy provides all actors involved in PRECINCT, with a list of the main relevant terms, along with their respective definitions and bibliographic references.

Table 1: Risk Taxonomy

Term	Definition
Absolute Risk	Level of risk expressed with standard units of measurement that allows for independent interpretation without comparison to estimates of other risks. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]

Absolute (unmitigated) Risk	Level of risk that exists without risk controls. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Acceptable Risk	The level of residual risk that has been determined to be a reasonable level of potential loss/disruption for a specific system. [Source: CIAO – Critical Infrastructure Assurance Office - U.S.A]
Accidental Hazard	Source of harm or difficulty created by negligence, error, or unintended failure. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Accountability	The property that ensures that the actions of an entity may be traced uniquely to the entity. [Source: ISO/IEC PDTR 13335-1] This may cover non-repudiation, deterrence, fault isolation, intrusion detection and prevention, and after-action recovery and legal action. [Source: ENISA]
Action	An act taken against an Asset by a Threat Agent. Requires first that contact occurs between the Asset and Threat Agent. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Adaptive Risk	Category of risk that includes threats intentionally caused by humans. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Adversary	Individual, group, organization, or government that conducts or has the intent to conduct detrimental activities. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Asset	The information, information system, or information system component that is breached or impaired by the Threat Agent in a manner whereby its value is diminished, or the act introduces liability to the Primary Stakeholder. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020] Anything that has value to the organization, its business operations and their continuity, including Information resources that support the organization's mission. [Source: ISO/IEC PDTR 13335-1]
Attack Method	Manner and means, including the weapon and delivery method, an adversary may use to cause harm on a target. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Attack Path	Steps that an adversary takes or may take to plan, prepare for, and execute an attack. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Baseline Risk	Current level of risk that takes into account existing risk mitigation measures. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Bayesian Probability	The process of evaluating the probability of a hypothesis through 1) the specification of a prior probability and 2) modification of the prior probability by incorporation of observed information to create an updated posterior probability. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Break-even Analysis	Variant of cost-benefit analysis that estimates the threshold value at which a policy alternative's costs equal its benefits. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Capability	Means to accomplish a mission, function, or objective. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Communication and consultation	Continual or iterative processes that an organization conducts to provide, share or obtain information and to engage in dialogue with stakeholders regarding the management of risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Consequence	Outcome of an event <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There can be more than one consequence from one event. - Consequences can range from positive to negative. - Consequences can be expressed qualitatively or quantitatively. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Consequence Assessment	Product or process of identifying or evaluating the potential or actual effects of an event, incident, or occurrence. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]

Contact Event	Occurs when a Threat Agent establishes a physical or virtual (e.g., network) connection to an Asset. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Contact Frequency (CF)	The probable frequency, within a given timeframe, that a Threat Agent will come into contact with an Asset. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Contingency Plan	A plan for emergency response, backup operations, and post-disaster recovery in a system, as part of a security program, to ensure availability of critical system resources and facilitate continuity of operations in a crisis. [Source: ENISA]
Control	<p>Any person, policy, process, or technology that has the potential to reduce the Loss Event Frequency (LEF) – Loss Prevention Controls – and/or Loss Magnitude (LM) – Loss Mitigation Controls. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]</p> <p>Measure to modify risk. Controls are the result of risk treatment. Controls include any process, policy, device, practice, or other actions designed to modify risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA)	Analytic technique that compares the cost of two or more alternatives with the same outcome. Alternatively: analytic technique that evaluates an alternative by how much it delivers per unit cost, or how much has to be spent per unit benefit. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)	Analytic technique used to compare alternatives according to the relative costs incurred and the relative benefits gained. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Countermeasure	Action, measure, or device intended to reduce an identified risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Criticality	Importance to a mission or function, or continuity of operations. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Criticality Assessment	Product or process of systematically identifying, evaluating, and prioritizing based on the importance of an impact to mission(s), function(s), or continuity of operations. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Data Availability	The fact that data is accessible and services are operational. [Source: ENISA]
Data Confidentiality	The protection of communications or stored data against interception and reading by unauthorized persons. [Source: ENISA]
Data Integrity	<p>The property that information is not made available or disclosed to unauthorized individuals, entities, or processes. [Source: ISO/IEC PDTR 13335-1]</p> <p>The confirmation that data which has been sent, received, or stored are complete and unchanged. [Source: ENISA]</p> <p>The property that data has not been altered or destroyed in an unauthorized manner. [Source: ISO/IEC PDTR 13335-1]</p>
Decision Analysis	Techniques, body of knowledge, and professional practice used to provide analytical support for making decisions through a formalized structure. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Definition of Scope	Process for the establishment of global parameters for the performance of Risk Management within an organization. Within the definition of scope for Risk Management internal and external factors have to be taken into account. [Source: ENISA]
Deterrent	Measure that discourages, complicates, or delays an adversary's action or occurrence by instilling fear, doubt, or anxiety. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Direct Consequence	Effect that is an immediate result of an event, incident, or occurrence. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]

Disaster Recovery	The process of restoring a system to full operation after an interruption in service, including equipment repair / replacement, file recovery / restoration. [Source: ENISA]
Economic Consequence	Effect of an incident, event, or occurrence on the value of property or on the production, trade, distribution, or use of income, wealth, or commodities. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Enterprise Risk Management	Comprehensive approach to risk management that engages organizational systems and processes together to improve the quality of decision making for managing risks that may hinder an organization's ability to achieve its objectives. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Evaluation	Process of examining, measuring and/or judging how well an entity, procedure, or action has met or is meeting stated objectives. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Event	Occurrence or change of a particular set of circumstances. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The event can be certain or uncertain. - The event can be a single occurrence or a series of occurrences. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Event Tree	Graphical tool used to illustrate the range, probability, and interaction of causal occurrences that lead to a final outcome. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Evidence	Information that either by itself or when used in conjunction with other information is used to establish proof about an event or action. Evidence does not necessarily prove truth or existence of something but contributes to establish proof. [Source: ENISA]
Exposure	The potential loss to an area due to the occurrence of an adverse event. [Source: ISACA] <p>Generally, in the Risk Management process, a risk does not always represent a loss or a negative consequence but can also be an opportunity or a result of a positive event. [Source: ENISA]</p> <p>Extent to which an organization is subject to an event. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
External Context	External environment in which the organization seeks to achieve its objectives [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
FAIR	Factor Analysis of Information Risk. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Fault Tree	Graphical tool used to illustrate the range and probabilities of possible outcomes that arise from an initiating event. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Frequency	Number of occurrences of an event per defined period of time or number of trials. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon] <p>Measure of the likelihood of an event expressed as a number of events or outcomes per defined unit of time. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Frequentist Probability	Interpretation or estimate of probability as the long-run frequency of the occurrence of an event as estimated by historical observation or experimental trials. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Function	Service, process, capability, or operation performed by an entity, asset, system, network, or geographic area. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Game Theory	Branch of applied mathematics that models interactions among agents where an agent's choice and subsequent success depend on the choices of other agents

	that are simultaneously acting to maximize their own results or minimize their losses. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Gap Analysis	A comparison that identifies the difference between the actual and the expected / specified system status. [Source: ENISA]
Hazard	Natural or man-made source or cause of harm or difficulty. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
	Potential source of harm. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Horizon Scanning	Process of identifying future trends, drivers, and/or conditions that may have an effect on future events, incidents, or occurrences. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Human Consequence (health)	Effect of an incident, event, or occurrence that results in injury, illness, or loss of life. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Impact	The result of an unwanted incident. [Source: ISO/IEC PDTR 13335-1]
Impact Analysis	The identification of critical business processes, and the potential damage or loss that may be caused to the organization resulting from a disruption to those processes. Business impact analysis identifies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the form the loss or damage will take - how that degree of damage or loss is likely to escalate with time following an incident - the minimum staffing, facilities and services needed to enable business processes to continue to operate at a minimum acceptable level - the time for full recovery of the business processes [Source: ENISA]
Implementation	Act of putting a procedure or course of action into effect to support goals or achieve objectives. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Incident	An event that has been assessed as having an actual or potentially adverse effect on the security or performance of a system. [Source: ENISA] Occurrence, caused by either human action or natural phenomena, that may cause harm and that may require action. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Indirect Consequence	Effect that is not a direct consequence of an event, incident, or occurrence, but is caused by a direct consequence, subsequent cascading effects, and/or related decisions. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Integrated Risk Management	Structured approach that enables the distribution and employment of shared risk information and analysis and the synchronization of independent yet complementary risk management strategies to unify efforts across the enterprise. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Intent	A state of mind or desire to achieve an objective. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Intentional Hazard	Source of harm, duress, or difficulty created by a deliberate action or a planned course of action. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Interested Party	Person or group having an interest in the performance or success of an organization's mission or objectives. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Internal Context	Internal environment in which the organization seeks to achieve its objectives. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Level of risk	Magnitude of a risk expressed in terms of the combination of consequences and their likelihood. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Likelihood	Chance of something happening, whether defined, measured or estimated objectively or subjectively, or in terms of general descriptors (such as rare, unlikely, likely, almost certain), frequencies, or probabilities.

	Likelihood Statistical is conditional probability of observing a particular event given the hypothesis under consideration is true. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Loss Event	Occurs when a Threat Agent's action (Threat Event) is successful in breaching or impairing an Asset. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Loss Event Frequency (LEF)	The probable frequency, within a given timeframe, that a Threat Agent will inflict harm upon an Asset. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Loss Flow	The structured decomposition of how losses materialize when a Loss Event occurs. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Loss Magnitude (LM)	The probable magnitude of loss resulting from a Loss Event. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Loss Scenario	The story of loss that forms a sentence from the perspective of the Primary Stakeholder. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Mission Consequence	Effect of an incident, event, operation, or occurrence on the ability of an organization or group to meet a strategic objective or perform a function. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Mitigation	Limitation of any negative consequence of a particular event. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73] Ongoing and sustained action to reduce the probability of, or lessen the impact of, an adverse incident. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Model	Approximation, representation, or idealization of selected aspects of the structure, behavior, operation, or other characteristics of a real-world process, concept, or system. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Monitor and Review	A process for measuring the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization's Risk Management processes is the establishment of an ongoing monitor and review process. This process makes sure that the specified management action plans remain relevant and updated. This process also implements control activities including re-evaluation of the scope and compliance with decisions. [Source: ENISA]
Monitoring	Continual checking, supervising, critically observing or determining the status in order to identify change from the performance level required or expected. Monitoring can be applied to a risk management framework, risk management process or a risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Natural Hazard	Source of harm or difficulty created by a meteorological, environmental, or geological phenomenon or combination of phenomena. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Net Assessment	Multidisciplinary strategic assessment process used to provide a comparative evaluation of the balance of strengths and weaknesses. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Network	Group of persons or components that share information or interact with each other in order to perform a function. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Normalised Risk	Measure of risk created by mathematically adjusting a value in order to permit comparisons. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Non-adaptive Risk	Category of risk that includes threats caused by natural and technological hazards. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Operational Risk	Risk that has the potential to impede the successful execution of operations [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Primary Stakeholder	The person or organization that owns or is accountable for an Asset. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]

Priority		Sequence in which an incident or problem needs to be resolved, based on impact and urgency. [Source: ENISA]
Probabilistic Assessment	Risk	Type of quantitative risk assessment that considers possible combinations of occurrences with associated consequences, each with an associated probability or probability distribution. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Probability		Extent to which an event is likely to occur. [Source: ENISA]
		Measure of the chance of occurrence expressed as a number between 0 and 1, where 0 is impossibility and 1 is absolute certainty. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Probability of Action (PoA)		The probability that a Threat Agent will act against an Asset once contact occurs. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Procedure		A written description of a course of action to be taken to perform a given task. [Source: ENISA]
Process		An organized set of activities which uses resources to transform inputs to outputs. [Source: ENISA]
Process Owner		An individual held accountable and responsible for the workings and improvement of one of the organization's defined processes and its related sub-processes. [Source: ENISA]
Psychological Consequence		Effect of an incident, event, or occurrence on the mental or emotional state of individuals or groups resulting in a change in perception and/or behavior. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Qualitative Assessment Methodology	Risk	Set of methods, principles, or rules for assessing risk based on non-numerical categories or levels. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Quantitative Assessment Methodology	Risk	Set of methods, principles, or rules for assessing risks based on the use of numbers where the meanings and proportionality of values are maintained inside and outside the context of the assessment. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Redundancy		Additional or alternative systems, sub-systems, assets, or processes that maintain a degree of overall functionality in case of loss or failure of another system, sub-system, asset, or process. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Relative Risk		Measure of risk that represents the ratio of risks when compared to each other or a control. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Residual Risk		Risk remaining after risk treatment. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
		Risk that remains after risk management measures have been implemented. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Resilience		Ability to adapt to changing conditions and prepare for, withstand, and rapidly recover from disruption. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
		Capacity to resist being affected by an event. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Resistance (RS)	Strength	The strength of a Control as compared to the probable level of force (as embodied by the time, resources, and technological capability; measured as a percentile) that a Threat Agent is capable of applying against an Asset. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Return on Investment (risk)		Calculation of the value of risk reduction measures in the context of the cost of developing and implementing those measures. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Review		Activity undertaken to determine the suitability, adequacy and effectiveness of the subject matter to achieve established objectives. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk		The probable frequency and probable magnitude of future loss. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]

	<p>The potential that a given threat will exploit vulnerabilities of an asset or group of assets and thereby cause harm to the organization. [Source: ISO/IEC PDTR 13335-1]</p> <p>Potential for an unwanted outcome resulting from an incident, event, or occurrence, as determined by its likelihood and the associated consequences. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p> <p>Effect of uncertainty on objectives. An effect is a deviation from the expected - positive and/or negative. Objectives can have different aspects such as financial, health and safety, and environmental goals and can apply at different levels such as strategic, organization-wide, project, product, and process. Risk is often characterized by reference to potential events, consequences, or a combination of these and how they can affect the achievement of objectives. Risk is often expressed in terms of a combination of the consequences of an event or a change in circumstances, and the associated likelihood of occurrence. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Risk Acceptance	<p>Decision to accept a risk by the responsible management of the organization. Risk acceptance depends on risk criteria defined within the process Definition of Scope. [Source: Definition adopted from ISO/IEC Guide 73 with some modification by ENISA]</p> <p>Informed decision to take a particular risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p> <p>Explicit or implicit decision not to take an action that would affect all or part of a particular risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>
Risk Aggregation	<p>Process to combine individual risks to obtain a more complete understanding of risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Risk Analysis	<p>The process to comprehend the nature of risk and determine the level of risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p> <p>Systematic examination of the components and characteristics of risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>
Risk Appetite	<p>Amount and type of risk an organization is prepared to pursue or take. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Risk Assessment	<p>The overall process of risk identification, risk analysis, and risk evaluation. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p> <p>Product or process which collects information and assigns values to risks for the purpose of informing priorities, developing or comparing courses of action, and informing decision making. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>
Risk Assessment Methodology	<p>Set of methods, principles, or rules used to identify and assess risks and to form priorities, develop courses of action, and inform decision making. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>
Risk Assessment Tool	<p>Activity, item, or program that contributes to determining and evaluating risks. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>

Risk Attitude	Organization's approach to assess and eventually pursue, take or refuse risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Aversion	Attitude to turn away from risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Avoidance	Decision not to become involved in, or action to withdraw from, a risk situation. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Communication	<p>Strategies or measures taken that effectively remove exposure to a risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p> <p>A process to exchange or share information about risk between the decision-maker and other stakeholders. The information can relate to the existence, nature, form, probability, severity, acceptability, treatment or other aspects of risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p> <p>Exchange of information with the goal of improving risk understanding, affecting risk perception, and/or equipping people or groups to act appropriately in response to an identified risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>
Risk Control	<p>Actions implementing risk management decisions. Risk control may involve monitoring, re-evaluation, and compliance with decisions. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p> <p>Deliberate action taken to reduce the potential for harm or maintain it at an acceptable level. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>
Risk Criteria	<p>Terms of reference by which the significance or risk is evaluated.</p> <p>Risk criteria can include associated cost and benefits, legal and statutory requirements, socio-economic aspects, the concerns of stakeholders, priorities and other inputs to the assessment. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Risk Data	Information on key components of risk that are outputs of or inputs to risk assessments and risk analyses. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Factors	The individual components that determine risk, including Loss Event Frequency, Loss Magnitude, Threat Event Frequency, etc. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Risk Estimation	<p>Process used to assign values to the probability and consequences of a risk.</p> <p>It can consider cost, benefits, the concerns of stakeholders and other variables, as appropriate for risk evaluation. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Risk Evaluation	Process of comparing the estimated risk against given risk criteria to determine the significance of risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Exposure	Contact of an entity, asset, system, network, or geographic area with a potential hazard. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Financing	Provision of funds to meet the cost of implementing risk treatment and related costs. Form of risk treatments involving contingent arrangements for the provision of funds to meet the financial consequences should they occur [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Governance	Actors, rules, practices, processes, and mechanisms concerned with how risk is analyzed, managed, and communicated. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Identification	<p>Process to find, list and characterize elements of risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p> <p>Process of finding, recognizing, and describing potential risks. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>
Risk Indicator	Measure that signals the potential for an unwanted outcome as determined by qualitative or quantitative analysis [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]

Risk Management	<p>Coordinated activities to direct and control an organization with regard to risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p> <p>The process, distinct from risk assessment, of weighing policy alternatives in consultation with interested parties, considering risk assessment and other legitimate factors, and selecting appropriate prevention and control options. [Source: ENISA]</p> <p>Process of identifying, analyzing, assessing, and communicating risk and accepting, avoiding, transferring or controlling it to an acceptable level considering associated costs and benefits of any actions taken. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>
Risk Management Alternatives Development	Process of systematically examining risks to develop a range of options and their anticipated effects for decision makers. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Management Audit	Systematic, independent and documented process for obtaining evidence and evaluating it objectively to determine the extent to which the risk management framework is adequate and effective [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Management Cycle	Sequence of steps that are systematically taken and revisited to manage risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Management Framework	Set of components that provide the foundations and organizational arrangements for designing, implementing, monitoring, reviewing and continually improving risk management processes throughout the organization [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Management Methodology	Set of methods, principles, or rules used to identify, analyze, assess, and communicate risk, and accept, avoid, transfer, or control it to an acceptable level considering associated costs and benefits of any actions taken. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Management Plan	<p>Document that identifies risks and specifies the actions that have been chosen to manage those risks. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p> <p>Document within the risk management framework specifying the approach, the management components and resources to be applied to the management of risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Risk Management Policy	Overall intentions and direction of an organization related to risk management. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Management Process	Systematic application of management policies, procedures and practices to the tasks of communicating, consulting, establishing the context, identifying, analyzing, evaluating, treating, monitoring and reviewing risk [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Management Strategy	Course of action or actions to be taken in order to manage risks. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Matrix	<p>Tool for ranking and displaying components of risk in an array. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p> <p>Tool for ranking and displaying risks by defining ranges for consequence and likelihood. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>

Risk Mitigation	Application of measure or measures to reduce the likelihood of an unwanted occurrence and/or its consequences. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon] Measures taken to reduce an undesired consequence. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Mitigation Option	Measure, device, policy, or course of action taken with the intent of reducing risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Optimization	Process, related to a risk to minimize the negative and to maximize the positive consequences and their respective probabilities. Risk optimization depends upon risk criteria, including costs and legal requirements. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Owner	Person or entity with the accountability and authority for managing the risk and any associated risk treatments [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Perception	Way in which a stakeholder views a risk, based on a set of values or concerns. Risk perception depends on the stakeholder's needs, issues and knowledge. Risk perception can differ from objective data. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73] Subjective judgment about the characteristics and/or severity of risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Profile	Description and/or depiction of risks to an entity, asset, system, network, or geographic area. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon] Description of a set of risks. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Reduction	Actions taken to lessen the probability, negative consequences or both, associated with a risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73] Decrease in risk through risk avoidance, risk control, or risk transfer. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Register	Record of information about identified risks. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Reporting	Form of communication intended to address particular internal or external stakeholders to provide information regarding the current state of risk and its management. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Retention	Acceptance of the burden of loss, or benefit of gain, from a particular risk. Risk retention includes the acceptance of risks that have not been identified. Risk retention does not include treatments involving insurance, or transfer by other means. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Score	Numerical result of a semi-quantitative risk assessment methodology [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk Sharing	Form of risk treatments involving the agreed distribution of risk with other parties. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Source	Anything which alone or in combination has the intrinsic potential to give rise to risk. There is no risk when another object, person or organization does not have an interaction with a risk source. A risk source can be tangible or intangible. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Risk Tolerance	Degree to which an entity, asset, system, network, or geographic area is willing to accept risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon] Organization's readiness to bear the risk after risk treatments in order to achieve its objectives. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]

Risk Transfer	<p>Sharing with another party the burden of loss or benefit of gain, for a risk. Legal or statutory requirements can limit, prohibit or mandate the transfer of certain risk. Risk transfer can be carried out through insurance or other agreements. Risk transfer can create new risks or modify existing risk. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p> <p>Action taken to manage risk that shifts some or all of the risk to another entity, asset, system, network, or geographic area. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p>
Risk Treatment	<p>Process of selection and implementation of measures to modify risk. Risk treatment measures can include avoiding, optimizing, transferring or retaining risk.</p> <p>Process of developing, selecting and implementing controls. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Risk-based Decision Making	Determination of a course of action predicated primarily on the assessment of risk and the expected impact of that course of action on that risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Risk-informed Decision Making	Determination of a course of action predicated on the assessment of risk, the expected impact of that course of action on that risk, as well as other relevant factors. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Safeguards	<p>Practices, procedures or mechanisms that reduce risk.</p> <p>The term 'safeguard' is normally considered to be synonymous with the term 'control'. [Source: ISO/IEC PDTR 13335-1]</p>
Scenario (risk)	Hypothetical situation comprised of a hazard, an entity impacted by that hazard, and associated conditions including consequences when appropriate. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Secondary Stakeholder	Individuals or organizations that may be affected by events that occur to Assets outside of their control. For example, consumers are Secondary Stakeholders in a scenario where their personal private information may be inappropriately disclosed or stolen. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Security	<p>All aspects related to defining, achieving, and maintaining data confidentiality, integrity, availability, accountability, authenticity, and reliability.</p> <p>A product, system, or service is considered to be secure to the extent that its users can rely on that it functions (or will function) in the intended way. [Source: ISO/IEC WD 15443-1]</p>
Semi-Quantitative Risk Assessment Methodology	Set of methods, principles, or rules to assess risk that uses bins, scales, or representative numbers whose values and meanings are not maintained in other contexts. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Sensitivity Analysis	Process to determine how outputs of a methodology differ in response to variation of the inputs or conditions. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Simulation	Model that behaves or operates like a given process, concept, or system when provided a set of controlled inputs. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Social Amplification of Risk	Distortion of the seriousness of a risk caused by public concern about the risk and/or about an activity contributing to the risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Source	Item or activity having a potential for a consequence [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Source Identification	Process to find, list and characterize sources [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Stakeholder	Any individual, group or organization that can affect, be affected by, or perceive itself to be affected by, a risk [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Strategic Foresight	Range of activities associated with longer range planning and alternative futures analysis. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]

Strategic Risk	Risk that affects an entity's vital interests or execution of chosen strategy, whether imposed by external threats or arising from flawed or poorly implemented strategy. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Subject Matter Expert	Individual with in-depth knowledge in a specific area or field. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Subject Probability	Interpretation or estimate of probability as a personal judgment or —degree of belief about how likely a particular event is to occur, based on the state of knowledge and available evidence. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
System	Any combination of facilities, equipment, personnel, procedures, and communications integrated for a specific purpose. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Target	Asset, network, system or geographic area chosen by an adversary to be impacted by an attack. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Threat	Anything that is capable of acting in a manner resulting in harm to an Asset and/or organization; for example, acts of God (weather, geological events, etc.), malicious actors, errors, failures. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020] Natural or man-made occurrence, individual, entity, or action that has or indicates the potential to harm life, information, operations, the environment, and/or property. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Threat Agent	Any agent (e.g., object, substance, human) that is capable of acting against an Asset in a manner that can result in harm. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Threat Assessment	Product or process of identifying or evaluating entities, actions, or occurrences, whether natural or man-made, that have or indicate the potential to harm life, information, operations, and/or property. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Threat Capability (TCap)	The probable level of force (as embodied by the time, resources, and technological capability) that a Threat Agent is capable of applying against an Asset. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Threat Community	A subset of the overall Threat Agent population that shares key characteristics. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Threat Event	Occurs when a Threat Agent acts against an Asset. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Threat Event Frequency (TEF)	The probable frequency, within a given timeframe, that a Threat Agent will act against an Asset. [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]
Threat Shifting	Response of adversaries to perceived countermeasures or obstructions, in which the adversaries change some characteristic of their intent to do harm in order to avoid or overcome the countermeasure or obstacle. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Unacceptable Risk	Level of risk at which, given costs and benefits associated with further risk reduction measures, action is deemed to be warranted at a given point in time. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Uncertainty	Degree to which a calculated, estimated, or observed value may deviate from the true value. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon] State, even partial, of deficiency of information related to or understanding or knowledge of an event, its consequence, or likelihood. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]
Value of Statistical Life (VSL)	Amount people are willing to pay to reduce risk so that on average one less person is expected to die from the risk. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Vulnerability (Vuln)	The probability that a Threat Event will become a Loss Event; probability that Threat Capability is greater than Resistance Strength. (Synonym: Susceptibility). [Source: The Open Group Standard - 2020]

	<p>The existence of a weakness, design, or implementation error that can lead to an unexpected, undesirable event compromising the security of the computer system, network, application, or protocol involved. [Source: ITSEC]</p> <p>Physical feature or operational attribute that renders an entity, asset, system, network, or geographic area open to exploitation or susceptible to a given hazard. Vulnerability as degree is a qualitative or quantitative expression of the level to which an entity, asset, system, network, or geographic area is susceptible to harm when it experiences a hazard [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]</p> <p>Intrinsic properties of something that create susceptibility to a source of risk that can lead to a consequence. [Source: ISO/IEC Guide 73]</p>
Vulnerability Assessment	Product or process of identifying physical features or operational attributes that render an entity, asset, system, network, or geographic area susceptible or exposed to hazards [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Willingness-to-Accept	Amount a person is willing to accept to forgo a benefit. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]
Willingness-to-Pay	Amount a person would be willing to pay, sacrifice, or exchange for a benefit. [Source: DHS Risk Lexicon]

1.2 Threat Taxonomies

Identifying threats is a major component of a comprehensive risk analysis process for any organization seeking to protect its sensitive data and helps determine what adverse events are relevant to the organization and must be controlled. Critical infrastructures are vital assets for public safety, economic welfare, and the national security of nations. Vulnerabilities of critical infrastructures have increased with the widespread use of information technologies. As Critical National Infrastructures are becoming more vulnerable to cyberattacks, their protection becomes a significant issue for any organization as well as nation [10].

Security is of key importance for the development of an individual and the society. Particularly the means for and the forms of an organized provision of security have changed dramatically throughout history, influenced significantly by constantly new technologies and scientific evidence. The globalization of the world, and thus indirectly of security, poses serious dilemmas to the modern society about how to continue basing its development on the fundamental requirements related to the free movement of goods, services and people, and, on the other hand, about how to keep threats at an acceptable risk level. The emergence of asymmetric forms of threat to national and international security is based on completely different assumptions and perceptions which we were used in the past based on the static approach of managing conventional threats. The changing social conditions and tensions caused by the rapid technological development found particular social environments totally unprepared for confronting the new global security situation and, above all, the newly emerging complex security threats. Dynamic changes and unexpected technological development have contributed to even greater complexity of this dimension. The fact that the modern society depends entirely on the functioning of technology makes this society even more vulnerable in terms of security.

The critical infrastructure of every country, ranging from oil pipelines to the electricity grids, from gas to water networks, from transportation to financial/banking systems, to the public administration, are increasingly electronically managed. The progressive introduction of network management, monitoring and control systems, as well as the interdependence that has arisen, has certainly improved the performance level of such infrastructure, but it has also allowed access to cyber criminals, with consequent cyber-attacks and the increased risk of a domino effect. Therefore, the scenario has become more and more complex in recent years, as the introduction of advanced technologies added new sources of potential risk alongside the traditional threats.

When it comes to the classification of threats, it is fundamental to understand in detail the categories of threats themselves. Naturally, threats arise not only from deliberate actions, but also from unintentional defects or other factors that cannot be fully influenced [11].

A focus on a part of the most exposed threats in the field of cyber threats. Cybersecurity attacks have continued to increase through the years 2020 and 2021, not only in terms of vectors and numbers but also in terms of their impact. This trend has increased the attack surface and [12]. the cybersecurity landscape has grown in terms of sophistication of attacks, their complexity and their impact. A series of cyber threats emerged and materialised in the course of 2020 and 2021. Based on the analysis presented in this report, the ENISA Threat Landscape 2021 identifies and focuses on the following 8 prime threat groups (Figure 3). These 8 threat groups are highlighted because of their prominence during the reporting period, their popularity and the impact that materialisation of these threats has had.

Figure 3: ENISA Threat Landscape 2021

The prime threats identified include:

- Ransomware
- Malware
- Cryptojacking
- E-mail related threats
- Threats against data
- Threats against availability and integrity
- Disinformation –misinformation
- Non-malicious threats
- Supply-chain attacks [13]

From a threat perspective, there is no research work that provides a high-level ontology of threats for CI. Rather than designing the threat taxonomy from scratch, the most practical approach to develop the threat taxonomy to CIs uses the set of threats which was collected during the literature scan and from other sources. Different taxonomies have been analysed and described in the following sub-paragraphs [14].

1.2.1 National Risk Assessments List of Hazards

The European Commission reported a generic classification of threats for CI in which natural hazards are distinguished from non-malicious man-made hazards and malicious man-made hazards.

From the overall list of hazards identified in the National Risk Assessments, the following ones are identified as the most important:

- Natural Hazards
 - Floods
 - Severe weather
 - Wild/Forest fires
 - Earthquakes
 - Pandemics/epidemics
 - Livestock epidemics
- Man-made hazards
 - Non malicious
 - Industrial accidents
 - Nuclear/radiological accidents
 - Transport accidents
 - Loss of critical infrastructure
 - Malicious
 - Cyber attacks
 - Terrorist attacks [15]

1.2.2 HITRUST Threat Catalogue

The HITRUST alliance have published a threat taxonomy where at the top level logical, physical, and organizational threats are distinguished.

The result is the HITRUST Threat Catalogue (Figure 4), which is intended to provide a mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive enumeration of threats and a mapping of these threats to specific technical, physical, and administrative controls. Threats have been categorized in what is thought to be a logical grouping of types, categories, and sub-categories. The threat catalogue has three types of threats, which are logical, physical, and organizational. Each type of threat will have categories such as intentional, unintentional, and force majeure. Sub-categories further refine the categories into specific descriptors of the threat activity. Each threat has a unique identifier consisting of the first character from the name of each hierarchical level combined with a numerical value [16].

Figure 4: HITRUST Threat Catalogue

1.2.3 ENISA - Threats Affecting ICS/SCADA Systems

In ENISA the most common threats affecting ICS/SCADA systems are shown (Figure 5). The main focus is to determine and list the main security threats, risk factors and attack scenarios that affect ICS/SCADA systems [17].

Figure 5: Threats affecting ICS/SCADA Systems

1.2.4 List of Threats from Terrorism

In the context of physical security risk assessments, a list of threats from terrorism has been proposed (Table 2). There is an increasing demand for physical security risk assessments in which the span of assessment usually encompasses threats from terrorism [18].

Table 2: List of threats from terrorism

Threat	Description
Theft / Burglary	Unlawful removal of property from the facility during and/or after business hours committed by lone motivated individuals (insiders/outside) or organized syndicates.
Robbery	Removal of valuables by force or threat of force or by fear. May occur during and/or after business hours and may be committed by motivated individual(s) or organized syndicates.
Public Order Incidents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Demonstrations and/or mass protest situations by organized groups in the facility. 2. Incidents involving employees or contractors e.g. labour disputes. 3. Fighting/rioting by unruly persons 4. Drunk and disorderly behaviour by individuals
Sabotage/Mischief	Hostile acts to sabotage, damage, destroy or disable operating systems and equipment in the facility. May be carried out by Disgruntled staff, Contractors / workmen who are unsupervised; or external parties who enter premises by unauthorized means; or external elements in collusion with disgruntled staff.
Stand-off Attack with Hand Thrown Devices	Subversive elements launch stand-off attacks using Molotov cocktail or other incendiary devices from outside perimeter.
Explosive Attack with Mail or Parcel Bombs	Sending explosives by normal mail or courier services. Commonly 2kg to 5 kg TNTNEQ are considered
Attack Against High Profile Individuals	Attacks against high profile visitors (politically, diplomatically or commercially important persons, local and foreign dignitaries)
Placement of Improvised Explosive Devices (IEDs)	Placement of an IED inside the premises. Such attacks may be carried out by subversive elements motivated by political or religious ideology. Commonly 2kg to 20kg TNTNEQ are considered, depending on the profiles of pedestrians accessing the facility
Attack by a vehicle carrying improvised explosive devices (VBIEDs)	The attack could be carried out by subversive elements who are motivated by political or religious ideology using IED concealed inside a vehicle. Commonly 200kg to 1000kg TNTNEQ are considered, depending on types of vehicles accessing the facility.
Attack with Chemical /Biological/Radiological Agents	Attack by subversive elements motivated by political or religious ideology to contaminate air supply and water sources via introduction of Chemical/Biological/Radiological agents into air-conditioning systems, water tanks etc or via releasing in public.
Armed Assailant Attack	Attack by a group of 5-7 adversaries armed with weapons, grenades or incendiary devices to kill, maim or even seize victims as hostages.

1.2.5 ENISA - Threats to Smart Hospitals

In the context of the healthcare sector, ENISA provided an overview of the cyberthreats faced by smart hospitals. The notion of smart hospitals is introduced when Internet of Things (IoT) components are supporting core

functions of a hospital. Threats to smart hospitals are, however, not limited to malicious actions in terms of their root cause. Human errors and system failures as well as third-party failures also play an important role. The risks that result from these threats and corresponding vulnerabilities are typically mitigated by a combination of organisational and technical security measures taken by smart hospitals which comprise good practices. An illustration providing an overview of the threats faced by smart hospitals is depicted in Figure 6 [19]

Figure 6: Threats to smart hospitals

1.2.6 Taxonomy of Operational Cyber Security Risks

Operational cyber security risks are defined as operational risks to information and technology assets that have consequences affecting the confidentiality, availability, or integrity of information or information systems. It is provided a taxonomy of operational cyber security risks that attempts to identify and organize the sources of operational cyber security risk into four classes: (1) actions of people, (2) systems and technology failures, (3) failed internal processes, and (4) external events. Each class is broken down into subclasses, which are described by their elements, as illustrated in Figure 7 [20].

1. Actions of People	2. Systems and Technology Failures	3. Failed Internal Processes	4. External Events
<p>1.1 Inadvertent</p> <p>1.1.1 Mistakes</p> <p>1.1.2 Errors</p> <p>1.1.3 Omissions</p> <p>1.2 Deliberate</p> <p>1.2.1 Fraud</p> <p>1.2.2 Sabotage</p> <p>1.2.3 Theft</p> <p>1.2.4 Vandalism</p> <p>1.3 Inaction</p> <p>1.3.1 Skills</p> <p>1.3.2 Knowledge</p> <p>1.3.3 Guidance</p> <p>1.3.4 Availability</p>	<p>2.1 Hardware</p> <p>2.1.1 Capacity</p> <p>2.1.2 Performance</p> <p>2.1.3 Maintenance</p> <p>2.1.4 Obsolescence</p> <p>2.2 Software</p> <p>2.2.1 Compatibility</p> <p>2.2.2 Configuration management</p> <p>2.2.3 Change control</p> <p>2.2.4 Security settings</p> <p>2.2.5 Coding practices</p> <p>2.2.6 Testing</p> <p>2.3 Systems</p> <p>2.3.1 Design</p> <p>2.3.2 Specifications</p> <p>2.3.3 Integration</p> <p>2.3.4 Complexity</p>	<p>3.1 Process design or execution</p> <p>3.1.1 Process flow</p> <p>3.1.2 Process documentation</p> <p>3.1.3 Roles and responsibilities</p> <p>3.1.4 Notifications and alerts</p> <p>3.1.5 Information flow</p> <p>3.1.6 Escalation of issues</p> <p>3.1.7 Service level agreements</p> <p>3.1.8 Task hand-off</p> <p>3.2 Process controls</p> <p>3.2.1 Status monitoring</p> <p>3.2.2 Metrics</p> <p>3.2.3 Periodic review</p> <p>3.2.4 Process ownership</p> <p>3.3 Supporting processes</p> <p>3.3.1 Staffing</p> <p>3.3.2 Funding</p> <p>3.3.3 Training and development</p> <p>3.3.4 Procurement</p>	<p>4.1 Disasters</p> <p>4.1.1 Weather event</p> <p>4.1.2 Fire</p> <p>4.1.3 Flood</p> <p>4.1.4 Earthquake</p> <p>4.1.5 Unrest</p> <p>4.1.6 Pandemic</p> <p>4.2 Legal issues</p> <p>4.2.1 Regulatory compliance</p> <p>4.2.2 Legislation</p> <p>4.2.3 Litigation</p> <p>4.3 Business issues</p> <p>4.3.1 Supplier failure</p> <p>4.3.2 Market conditions</p> <p>4.3.3 Economic conditions</p> <p>4.4 Service dependencies</p> <p>4.4.1 Utilities</p> <p>4.4.2 Emergency services</p> <p>4.4.3 Fuel</p> <p>4.4.4 Transportation</p>

Figure 7: Taxonomy of Operational Risk

1.2.7 Taxonomy and Risk Assessment on the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT)

A taxonomy of the Security & Privacy issues of IoMT has been provided along with an approach to quantify IoMT risks and demonstrate how to assess risks in two IoMT devices. As the number of devices (things) connected to the Internet (Internet of things: IoT) is growing, achieving robust security and privacy (S&P) is becoming increasingly challenging. With the heavy use of medical things (MT), the S&P in the medical domain poses a serious issue that continues to grow. Due to the criticality and sensitivity of the data in the healthcare domain, ensuring the S&P of the Internet of medical things (IoMT) makes matters even more problematic. The taxonomy is based on several main dimensions, namely, IoT layers, possible intruders, compromise level, attack impact, attack method, CIA compromise, attack origin, attack level, and attack difficulty as shown in Figure 8 [21].

Figure 8: Security and Privacy IoMT Taxonomy

1.2.8 ENISA Threat Taxonomy

The ENISA has analysed and integrated available threat taxonomies in the current version of the ENISA taxonomy. The last updated document in this area, which was made by ENISA, is “ENISA Threat Taxonomy – A tool for structuring threat information”. The methodology used by ENISA is based primarily on a very detailed analysis of all the threats associated with cyberspace and have a direct impact on the operation of ECI as a whole. The classification developed by ENISA is shown in detail in Figure 9. ENISA in its classification identifies the following main sets of threats, such as:

- Legal threats,
- Unintentional data damage
- Disasters
- Damage/loss IT assets
- Failures or Malfunction
- Outages
- Eavesdropping, Interception, Hijacking
- Nefarious Activity, Abuse
- Deliberate physical attacks [22].

In advance, each main threat is further divided in detail in the form of specific threats to the functioning of ECI.

Figure 9: ENISA Threat Taxonomy

1.3 Projects Taxonomies

Other threat taxonomies have been produced in the context of EU projects.

1.3.1 SATIE Project

SATIE² project creates new 'Security Operation Centre' philosophies for inclusion in a comprehensive airport security policy. SATIE develops an interoperable toolkit that help improve cyber-physical correlations, forensic investigations and dynamic impact assessment at airports on the cyber and physical threat scenarios typical of attacks that threaten airport infrastructures and the results of a risk analysis applied to these scenarios. Threats included in the risk assessment are reported from Table 3 to Table 8 and listed:

- Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations (Safety)
 - Risks related to accidental conducts or situations (e.g. crowd in panic, developer mistake, lack of personnel etc.).
- Environmental Risk (Safety)
 - Risks related to environmental causes (e.g. inadequate microclimate environment, blackout, air conditioning malfunctioning etc.)
- Natural Risk (Safety)
 - Risks related to natural causes (e.g. bad weather conditions, earthquake, epidemic, fire etc.)
- Technical Risk (Safety/Security)
 - Risks related to technical causes (e.g. communication equipment failure, application software and/or hardware malfunctioning, message routing problems etc.)
- Terrorism and Sabotage (Security)
 - Risks related to terrorism and sabotage
- Political and social (Security)
 - Risks related to political and social related issue (e.g. war, demonstrations etc.) [23].

² <https://satie-h2020.eu/>

Table 3: SATIE Threat Taxonomy (a)

Macro-Category	Threat Category	Threat	Threat Description
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Crowd in panic	An unmanageable crowd which, in panic, can hurt people.
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Developer Mistake	Loss of data integrity or service availability as a result of developer mistakes
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Errors in Exercise of Personal Data Subject Rights	Errors in the exercise of the rights of interested parties regarding the processing of personal data
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Lack of Personnel	The number of workers is reduced on the basis of prolonged absences for any reason (illness, accident, maternity, etc..) or for dismissal
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Maintenance Error	Loss of data integrity or service availability due to errors committed by maintenance personnel qualified to work on specific systems or applications
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Non Conformity to Mandatory Laws and Standards	Non-compliance of policies and corporate security requirements
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Non-Compliance with Corporate Security Policies	The failure to meet legal requirements with the consequent risk of running into administrative or criminal penalties
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Operator Mistake	Loss of data integrity or service availability due to errors committed by operators authorized to operate on specific systems or applications
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Personnel Tiredness-Stress	Loss of data integrity or service availability due to errors, inaccuracies or misstatements committed by personnel involved in operations on the systems and applications with medium-high privilege levels
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	Reduced or Absent Technical Skills	Skills residing in few people or a threat of loss of any type of personnel with specific skills (through quitting, maternity leave, etc.)
Safety	Accidental Conducts or Accidental Situations	System Analyst Error	Loss of data integrity or service availability due to errors committed by personnel qualified to install, configure and maintain - directly or indirectly - systems, applications or proprietary systems
Safety	Environmental Causes	Air Conditioning Malfunctioning	Destruction or damage of a system or a part of it as a consequence of the monitoring/control system malfunctioning due to temperature and/or humidity.
Safety	Environmental Causes	Dust Particles	Damage of a system or of a part of it and/or loss/modification of data as consequence of dust deposit and/or particles capable of causing destructive micro short circuits in the electronic circuit boards that make up the system

Table 4: SATIE Threat Taxonomy (b)

Macro-Category	Threat Category	Threat	Threat Description
Safety	Environmental Causes	Electromagnetic Interference (EMI)	Hardware device interference produced by electromagnetic radiation and consequent loss/modification of processed, stored, or in-transit data.
Safety	Environmental Causes	Heavy Voltage Reduction (brownout)	Inability of the companies that supply voltage to provide the service within an acceptable range (e.g. 200-240 volts) that may cause problems on electrical components including reducing their life cycle or damaging them permanently
Safety	Environmental Causes	Inadequate Microclimate Environment	Unavailability of drinking water, necessary to ensure the hygienic conditions of the rooms and offices; uncomfortable climate in terms of ventilation, lighting, etc..
Safety	Environmental Causes	Lack of Electric Current (blackout)	The power devices may be interrupted in their operation, causing loss/modification of the processed data besides data unavailability
Safety	Environmental Causes	Minimums, Peaks and Surges	Temporary or rapid voltage level changes and surges that can cause operation system interruptions and/or processed data loss/modification besides their unavailability.
Safety	Environmental Causes	Nuclear radiation	It refers to a nuclear accident with consequences on infrastructure and people
Safety	Natural Causes	Bad Weather Conditions	Destruction of a system or a part of it as a consequence of hurricanes, tornadoes, snow storms, or any other high-intensity storms.
Safety	Natural Causes	Earthquake	Destruction of a system or a part of it as a consequence of tectonic movements
Safety	Natural Causes	Epidemic	Epidemic contagion within the company staff that affects their activities for a significant period of time
Safety	Natural Causes	Fire	Fire in the rooms where the system, its memory, or any paper with data on it are located.
Safety	Natural Causes	Flooding	Flooding of the rooms where the system and/or media storage is located (due to pipes or fixtures breaking).
Safety	Natural Causes	inability to use the enrolled credentials to login	A user, for some reason, cannot use the enrolled biometric elements to authenticate themselves.
Safety	Natural Causes	Jumps in Temperature or Humidity	Destruction or damage of a system (or a part of it) as a consequence of jumps in temperature in the room where the system and/or its memory is located.
Safety	Natural Causes	Lightning	Destruction of a system or a part of it as a consequence of a lightning strike.
Safety	Natural Causes	Pandemic	Global pandemic contagion that affects the organization's business and its relations with the commercial world

Table 5: SATIE Threat Taxonomy (c)

Macro-Category	Threat Category	Threat	Threat Description
Safety / Security	Organizational Events	Lost	A physical asset is lost.
Safety / Security	Organizational Events	Undefined Internal Roles and Responsibilities	Functional charts and organizational charts incorrectly defined or lacking mapped responsibilities within the organization
Safety / Security	Safety Accidents	Hardware Malfunctioning Repetition	Situations in which the same type of incident is repeated on the same asset continuously
Safety / Security	Safety Accidents	Repetition of Anomalies Related to Personnel Mistakes	Personnel repetition of activities which involve errors or anomalies or situations that do not conform with the policies and procedures
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Application Software Malfunctioning	Unavailability, loss and/or modification of processed or in-transit data due to an application software malfunctioning
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Basic Software Malfunctioning	Unavailability, loss and/or modification of processed or in-transit data due to an operating system and third-party software malfunctioning
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Communication Equipment Failure	Loss of data and service availability as a consequence of communication equipment malfunction or failure.
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Error in detecting danger/violation (false negatives)	The failure (human or machine) in detecting danger or a violation of an object.
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Forbidden Access to Network, Basic Software, Applications	Loss of data confidentiality, integrity and availability as a result of unauthorized access (voluntary or involuntary) to the telecommunication network (sharing), basic software and/or applications
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Forbidden Access to Storage Devices	Loss of confidentiality, integrity and availability of data as a consequence of unauthorized access (voluntary or involuntary) to storage devices
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Hardware Malfunctioning	Unavailability, loss and/or modification of processed or in-transit data as a consequence of hardware malfunctions of the system or parts of it.
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Logic Bomb, Trap Doors	Code portions included in the system which, when triggered by particular events, perform destructive actions on the data, applications, and/or systems
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Malware Software (Virus, Worm, Trojan, etc.)	Software created with the only purpose of causing damage, more or less extended to the systems on which it runs automatically (worms) or unknowingly by users (Virus, Trojan)
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Message Routing Problems	Loss of confidentiality, integrity and availability of data as a consequence of routing problems of the traffic to and from the source(s) to the legitimate destination(s)

Table 6: SATIE Threat Taxonomy (d)

Macro-Category	Threat Category	Threat	Threat Description
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Network Overload	Unavailability, loss and/or modification of data in transit due to network data transport overload
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Personal Data Breach	An uncontrolled personal data breach during the processing of personal data
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Storage Media Deterioration	Loss of data and services availability as a consequence of deterioration/breakdown of storage media
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Theft (Data breach)	Misappropriation of data for fraudulent and illegitimate purposes, in order to cause various kinds of damage, such as the unavailability of data and services, the theft of data or unauthorized access.
Safety / Security	Technical Causes	Utility Malfunctioning	Loss of data and service availability as a consequence of the utility malfunctioning
Safety / Security	Third Parties Report	Not Supported Basic Software	Situations where the vendor does not provide support and patches for the operating system version
Safety / Security	Third Parties Report	Not Supported Third-party Software	Situations in which providers do not supply patches or changes to the application software
Safety / Security	Third Parties Report	Supplier Unavailability	Situations in which the suppliers are not able to hold down services as a result of strikes, reduced staff or deliberate actions
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Abusive Entrance (Piggyback, Tailgating)	Illegal access to a system by "tagging along" with an authorized person
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Bomb	Destruction of the system or parts of it, storage systems and equipment following the explosion of bombs or other material which could cause explosions
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Communication Infiltrations	Unauthorized entry into the communication between two or more parties (Man-in-the-middle) for the purposes of espionage or data theft
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Denial of Service (DoS)	Unavailability of an access service by users, applications and networks
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	False Information Insertion	Inserting incorrect information into a system by authorized personnel
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Hijacking	A vehicle (or airplane) is hijacked, including to the wrong gate. This could also happen by tampering information sent to the driver/pilot.
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Information Management Equipment Tampering	Impairment of the integrity, availability and confidentiality of processed or in-transit data through equipment tampering or system tampering
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Intimidation	Theft of credentials or data and/or unauthorized access to systems and rooms by techniques of coercion or extortion (even through practices of social engineering)

Table 7: SATIE Threat Taxonomy (e)

Macro-Category	Threat Category	Threat	Threat Description
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Masquerading	Masquerading of a person who provides a false identity to a system in order to earn unauthorized access
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Melee attack	Any combat which involves directly striking a person at a range of less than a meter, especially using a meter, especially using martial arts or a melee weapon such as knives, etc.
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Physical attack and consequent unauthorized access to the secured zone	Any kinds of physical attack that aims to break a barrier by a physical attack (bombing, striking with a heavy vehicle, etc.).
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Scavenging	Scavenging information (discs, records, tapes) to gain access to the system and/or rooms
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Technological Equipment Tampering	Impairment of technological equipment functioning (air conditioning, fire sprinkler systems, access control)
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Unnoticed Data Subtraction (Salami Attack, Rounding)	Collecting of information in very small quantities in an unnoticed way, even by using Trojan Horse
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Vehicle-ramming attack	A vehicle-ramming attack is an assault in which a perpetrator deliberately rams a vehicle into a building or crowd of people.
Security	Terrorism and Sabotage	Wiretapping	Wiretapping of electromagnetic waves or telecommunication cables for the purposes of espionage or involuntary wiretapping of wires and cables during maintenance work.
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Compromised people (cyber, no security clearance)	Compromised people with no clearance seek to create cyber damage to the organization through malicious actions on cyber assets
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Compromised people (physical, no security clearance)	Compromised people with no clearance seek to create physical damage to the organization through malicious actions on physical assets
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Compromised personnel (cyber, high security clearance)	Compromised personnel with high clearance seek to create cyber damage to the organization through malicious actions on cyber assets
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Compromised personnel (cyber, medium security clearance)	Compromised personnel with medium clearance seek to create cyber damage to the organization through malicious actions on cyber assets
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Compromised personnel (physical, high security clearance)	Compromised personnel with high clearance seek to create physical damage to the organization through malicious actions on physical assets

Table 8: SATIE Threat Taxonomy (f)

Macro-Category	Threat Category	Threat	Threat Description
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Compromised personnel (physical, medium security clearance)	Compromised personnel with medium clearance seek to create physical damage to the organization through malicious actions on physical assets
Security	Voluntary Conducts	False enrolment	When a system is initialized with false biometric credentials that pertain to the attacker and not to the legitimate person whose account is being enrolled in the system.
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Listening to Unauthorized Communications	Voluntary or involuntary listening to confidential information
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Repudiation	Possibility that a particular sender of a generic message (email, IP packet, ticket, etc.) may afterwards deny having sent the message itself. The sender can be represented by an individual but also by an application
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Social Engineering	An attacker uses social engineering techniques to gain access to confidential information (in read/write or read only) or to restricted areas
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Theft (Physical)	Misappropriation of hardware, software, or equipment for fraudulent and illegitimate purposes, in order to cause various kinds of damage, such as the unavailability of data and services, the theft of data or unauthorized access.
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Unauthorized Access to Physical Areas	Unauthorized access gained to the building in a fraudulent way
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Unauthorized Network and Resource Use	Fraudulent and unauthorized use of network telecommunications with a consequent deterioration of the availability of resources and a decline in the service level provided and resource performance available.
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Unauthorized Software Use	Loss of data integrity and confidentiality as a result of unauthorized use of software, including misuse and abuse, not in line with the company's policy (which risk damages, including financial, reputational, physical, etc.)
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Unauthorized storage device use	Unauthorized use of storage devices for purposes of data theft
Security	Voluntary Conducts	Wrongful Use of Company Software	Software use for wrongful or purposes other than those permitted and approved by the company and/or the organization's policy

1.3.2 DEFENDER Project

DEFENDER³ adapts, integrates, upscales, deploys and validates a number of different technologies and operational blueprints with a view to develop a new approach to safeguard existing and future European CEI operation over cyber-physical-social threats, based on a) novel protective concepts for lifecycle assessment, resilience and self-healing offering “security by design” and b) advanced intruder inspection and incident mitigation systems. Moreover, DEFENDER creates a culture of security, where trusted information exchange between trained employees and volunteers complements cyber-physical protection, while preserving the privacy of the citizens involved.

The methodology of ENISA has been used in a detailed definition of all the threats that directly or indirectly affect the performance of electro-energy sector and upgraded with individual parts of the ENTSO-E methodologies and analyses carried out by the Institute for Corporate Security Studies on execution of risk assessments of electro-energy facilities in the Republic of Slovenia. The scope of those threats also includes those threats which are supposed to become an important factor in the area only in the near future. Especially in this context, the artificial intelligence that will in the future become a reality when used in the area of electro-energy sector was exposed. This already today opens certain dilemmas with the safety aspects which will need to be taken into consideration if we are to talk about a comprehensive approach to the management of safety risks. However, despite the fact that ENISA typologies already envisaged them, the individual main factors of threats were further elaborated and defined. In particular, highlighting the technical factors of the threats that were almost entirely omitted in the typology of ENISA, or they touched only the information and communication field. Each of the main carriers on this proposed typology of threats, comes from the study of DEFENDER.

The main carriers were meaningfully defined and divided into seven basic groups shown in the Figure 10 below [24].

Figure 10: General CEI threats structure

In the DEFENDER project, the threats have been divided according to six different levels starting from the general level to the more specific one. The following Table 9, Table 10, Table 11 and Table 12 show the DEFENDER detailed delineation of threats according to the main groups:

³ <https://defender-project.eu/>

Table 9: DEFENDER detailed delineation of threats on the main groups (a)

Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Level 6	
Natural disasters (external)	Meteorological	Strong wind (Hurricane, Tornado) Flooding Extreme cold (snowfall, ice rail) Extreme precipitation, included land slides Lightning (thunder stroke) Electromagnetic storm				
	Environmental disasters	Fires Dangerous radiation leaks Pollution Dust Corrosion Unfavourable climatic conditions Major events in the environment Explosions				
	Geological/Geotechnical	Snow slide Land slide Earthquake Tsunami Volcanism				
	Fire	Forest wildfire Ling grass				
	Cosmic	Solar flare Objects				
Medical/Biological (Internal/External)	Human	Household disease Pandemics				
	Wildlife					
Technical	Random Failure	Line break				
		Tower break Substations/Transformers				
	Systemic failures, aging	Line break Tower break Substations/Transformers Structural Collapse				
	Accident fire (internal)	Transformer, substation Control room				
	Nearby accident (external)	Industrial fire/explosion Transportation (rail, road, aviation, marine) Toxic release				
	Failure, Malfunction of support systems	ICT	Failures of parts of devices		Line cards Connectors	
			Device or system failures		Network devices Servers Data centres	
			Failure or disruption of communication links (communication networks)		Cable break Cable cut	
Failures or disruptions of main supply				Power Cooling Water		
Failure or disruption of service providers (supply chain)						
Failure or disruptions of service power supply						
Malfunction of devices or system		Network devices Services				

Table 10: DEFENDER detailed delineation of threats on the main groups (b)

		Tower break Substations/Transformers			
	Systemic failures, aging	Line break Tower break Substations/Transformers Structural Collapse			
	Accident fire (internal)	Transformer, substation Control room			
	Nearby accident (external)	Industrial fire/explosion Transportation (rail, road, aviation, marine) Toxic release			
	Failure, Malfunction of support systems	ICT	Failures of parts of devices	Line cards Connectors	
			Device or system failures	Network devices Servers Data centres	
			Failure or disruption of communication links (communication networks)	Cable break Cable cut	
			Failures or disruptions of main supply	Power Cooling Water	
			Failure or disruption of service providers (supply chain)		
			Failure or disruptions of service power supply		
			Malfunction of devices or system	Network devices Services	
		Fault location Assessment of switching status Standing phase angles Low frequency isolation scheme Intentional islanding Local load shedding Under-frequency and switched capacitor relays			
Human unintentional	Failure	Control room operator Maintenance crew			
	Unintentional data and systems damage	Erroneous information sharing or leakage Erroneous use or administration of devices, systems Usage of information from unreliable source Unintentional alteration of data/ change of data in an informational system			
		Inadequate design, planning, or lack of adaptation	Inadequate specifications Inadequate usability Insecure interfaces (APIs) Policy/procedure flaws Design errors		
Human Intentional behaviour (insider, outsider)	Malicious acts (physical)	Terrorism, destruction of critical components (bomb attack threat) Manipulation of SCADA Sabotage Vandalism Theft (device, media, material) Information leakage, sharing Unauthorized physical access Hijacking of the key personnel			

Table 11: DEFENDER detailed delineation of threats on the main groups (c)

		Using drones as an attack platform				
	Malicious acts (cyber)	Eavesdropping, Interception, Hijacking	War driving Intercepting, compromising emissions			
			Interception of information	Espionage	Nation state espionage Corporate espionage	
				Rogue hardware Software interception		
			Interring radiation Man in the middle, session hijacking Repudiation of actions Network reconnaissance, information gathering Replay of messages			
		Nefarious Activity, Abuse	Identity theft (fraud) Unsolicited & infected e-mail			
			Denial of service	Volume	Amplification/Reflection Spoofing Flooding	
				Application	Ping of Death Win Nuke XDoS	
			Malicious code, Software activity Social Engineering Abuse of Information Leakage			
				Generation and use of rouge certificates	SSL CA Infiltration	Diginotar
				Manipulation of HW and SW		
		Manipulation of information	Rutting table manipulation			
			DNS manipulation	DNS Spoofing DNS poisoning		
			Falsification of configuration			
			AS manipulation	AS Hijacking		
		Misuse of audit tools Falsification of records Misuse of information, information systems Unauthorized use of administration of devices & systems				
		Unauthorized access to information systems/network	IMPI Protocol DNS Register Hijacking	IMPI Protocol DNS Register Hijacking		
		Unauthorized software installation Unauthorized use of software Compromising confidential information Abuse of authorizations Hoax				
		Bad ware	Virus Worm Trojan Root kit			

Table 12: DEFENDER detailed delineation of threats on the main groups (d)

				Botnets Spyware Scareware Rogue ware Adware Geyware	
			Remote activity (execution) Target attacks (Including ATP)		
		Damage, Loss of IT assets	Damage caused by third party	External case Internal case	
			Loss from DMR conflicts Loss of (integrity of) sensitive information Loss or destruction of devices, storage media and documents Loss of information in the cloud Information leakage Damage, corruption from testing		
Management, organizational, legal and operational activities (inside/outside)	Lack of security culture, risk awareness	Top management Control room operators Other relevant actors			
	Lack of knowledge				
	Inadequate Institutional programs	Lack of surveillance security relevant activities Tree cutting programs			
	Inappropriate public procurements Legal	Unauthorized use of copyright material Failure to meet contractual agreements (requirements)			
		Judiciary decision/court order Violation of laws or regulation, breach of legislation	No-IP Microsoft domains seizure		
Market/economic related	Undue economic pressure				

1.3.3 PANOPTIS Project

The purpose of PANOPTIS⁴ project was to improve the resiliency (ability to adapt) of the road infrastructures and ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, landslides, and earthquakes. The project’s main goal was to combine down-scale climate change scenarios (applied to road infrastructure) with structural and geotechnical simulation tools, and with actual data from sensors (terrestrial and airborne), in order to provide the operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at planning, maintenance and operation level.

In the context of PANOPTIS project a taxonomy has been developed with the purposes of Climate, Atmospheric Forcing and Multi-Hazard Modelling and development of multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules and Assessment Toolkit for RI (Geo)Structures.

The **Hazards and threats for Road Infrastructure taxonomy** categorises the hazards according to the following criteria:

- Hazard: Extreme weather conditions** (such as storm surge, flooding, strong wind, extreme heat, extreme cold, fog)

Examples of potential impact on RI and Operations/Maintenance:

- Damage to, or inaccessibility of, low-lying coastal infrastructure such as roads and railway beds, tunnels, and underground subway corridors.
- Increased thermal cracking of pavements and runways.
- Increased fatigue failure for most transport infrastructures (TI), particularly roads.

⁴ <http://www.panoptis.eu/>

- (d) Greater likelihood of RI/TI failure and disruptions of transport operations for all transport modes.
- (e) Increased threats to bridges and auxiliary infrastructure such as road signs, traffic signals, overpasses, and toll stations.
- (f) Damage to overhead lines for power supply, signs, lighting features, and increased tree fall leading to the closure of roads.
- (g) Safety hazards for vehicles.

2. Hazard: Geological hazards (earthquakes, landslides)

Examples of potential impact on RI and Operations/Maintenance:

- (a) Damages to bridges
- (b) Failure of embankment and drainage structures
- (c) Traffic Disruption

3. Hazard: Man-made events

Examples of potential impact on RI and Operations/Maintenance:

- (a) Closure of the RI/TI, especially in critical parts, such as tunnels, bridges.
- (b) Disruptions of transport operations for all transport modes.
- (c) Structural damage to bridges or other RI/TI elements.

1.3.4 STAR-TRANS Project

The objective of STAR-TRANS⁵ was to develop a comprehensive Transportation Security Risk Assessment Framework for assessing related risk and provide coherent contingency management procedures in interconnected, interdependent and heterogeneous transport networks. The aim of proposed Transportation Security Risk Assessment Framework is to formalise the linkage between risk incidents, transportation network assets and dependency types between assets in order to assess the impact of an incident on the affected interconnected and interdependent networks. The proposed Transportation Security Risk Assessment Framework consists of a modelling formalism to specify transportation network structure, assets and dependencies between assets, as well as ICT-based supporting tools to generate impact assessment reports on interconnected and interdependent transportation networks in cases of risk incidents.

In the context of STAR-TRANS project, the **STAR-TRANS Transportation Security Risk Analysis Framework** has been developed with the purposes of assessing transport-related risks and consequently formulate coherent contingency management procedures to be applied on interconnected, interdependent and heterogeneous transport networks.

The basic principle of the proposed Risk Analysis Framework (reported in STAR-TRANS D1.2) is that each network will be modeled starting from its assets, i.e., objects with specific and easily recognizable roles.

Assets are divided into two groups:

1. Direct assets

- (a) Passengers, goods, services relating to the motivation to transport
- (b) Transport media (movable assets)
- (c) Transport Infrastructure

2. Indirect assets

- (a) Energy

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/225594/reporting>

(b) Information

Asset interconnection is defined through four distinct categories:

1. **Physical Interdependency**, arising from a physical linkage between the inputs and outputs of two assets.
2. **Systems Interdependency**, defined from certain properties of the system transmitted through another asset
3. **Geographic Interdependency**, occurring when elements of multiple assets are in close spatial proximity.
4. **Logical Interdependency**, if the state of each asset depends on the state of other assets via a mechanism that is not any of the above.

A generalized and common **Risk Analysis Framework (RAF)** is defined for interconnected and heterogeneous transportation networks based on a repetitive process of risk evaluation and assessment of severity, taking into account the Likelihood of occurrence and the Consequences.

Likelihood is the frequency of occurrence of a particular threat. In a more generic approach it is expressed by the formula: Likelihood = Intention to harm X Capability to succeed.

The levels of Likelihood are classified into a five category system with values of 'Very Low', 'Low', 'Medium', 'High' and 'Certainty'.

Consequences are the result of the realization of a threat and defined as the harmful or damaging effects of a possible or realized emergency or threat. Consequences can be characterized in the following qualitative and quantitative ways:

- **Range:** relative to the radius of the geographic area likely to be affected by the loss or non-availability of the critical asset.
- **Severity:** the consequences of the malfunction or damage/destruction based on the following criteria:
 - ✓ The impact on the public (affected population, losses).
 - ✓ The financial impact (level of economic loss or/and degradation of products and services).
 - ✓ The impact on the reputation and prestige of the operator.
 - ✓ The environmental impact.
 - ✓ The social and psychological impact
 - ✓ The cascading effects on other critical infrastructures and technologically related incidents.
 - ✓ The impact on the transportation network itself and the interconnected networks.

Consequences have been described and classified based on the following internationally acceptable five category scheme with values of 'Negligible', 'Small', 'Medium', 'High' and 'Severe'.

Finally, **Risk** is estimated using a five-category system, in accordance to the previous classification of likelihood and consequences with values of 'Very Low', 'Low', 'Medium', 'High' and 'Critical'.

Concerning asset interconnection and the propagation of risk, the basic premise used for modelling risk propagation, is that an incident which initiates in a specific asset of any transportation network can cause diverse impacts and affect other interconnected assets or networks.

Furthermore, —impacts from security incidents in an asset can trigger incidents in interconnected assets, defined in a series of steps:

Step 1: Scenario outline definition and description of the initial incident(s) that occur(s).

Step 2: Estimate Risk of incident in the Asset.

Step 3: Determine the interconnected Assets.

Step 4: Estimate Risk in interconnected asset, based on an impact propagation matrix.

The kick-off point for assessing risk incidents will be a user-based scenario. A scenario exploits threats in a network in the form of incidents occurring in specific assets of the network. The above methodology is used for calculating consequences and propagating the risk throughout the network of networks.

Scenarios will be defined by the users of our tool, which can be the operators of a network, security experts, governmental security enforcement organizations etc.

An Impact Assessment Modelling Language was defined as part of the work implemented in the STAR-TRANS project in order to support this scenario driven risk assessment methodology.

Threat categorization

- Intentional Acts
 - Organized & common crime
 - Terrorism
 - Antisocial behavior
 - Hooliganism
- Mass demonstrations
 - Strikes
- Technological Accidents & Fires
 - Environmental accidents
 - Technological accidents
 - Transport of hazardous materials
 - Collapsing of infrastructures
 - Urban fires
- Natural Events
 - Extreme weather
 - Earthquakes
 - Flooding
 - Biological
 - Wildfires
- Systems interference
 - IT system
 - SCADA
 - Signaling system
 - Energy supply network
 - Data tampering
 - Unavailability of information and critical systems
- Other
 - Abandoned objects
 - Bad publicity
 - Obstructing security measures
 - Absence of personnel
 - Unavailability of services and assets
 - Panic
 - False alarms

The following risk taxonomy shown in Table 13 was developed as part of STAR-TRANS consequences matrix. Each threat can be ranked in terms of likelihood (example: 0 = non likely, 1= likely).

Table 13: STAR-TRANS Risk Taxonomy

Threat	Terrorism (internal and international)																	
Incident	Bomb attacks / explosives with high power	Bombs in abandoned objects	Homicide attempt or homicide	Launch of antitank or other type missile	Armed robbery or theft in vehicles	Armed robbery or theft in location of money storage or counting	Vehicle bomb	Kidnapping / hostage of company personnel and/or passengers	Seizure of vehicle or installation / station	Incendiary	Sabotage	Letter with infectious or explosive material	Electronic attack / cyber crime (hacking, cracking, phishing)	Dirty bombs (CBRN)	Suicide commando vehicle	Non-conventional weapons (CBRN) in installations / stations / air handling systems		
Threat	Anarchism								Organised and common crime									
Incident	Improvised incendiary devices	Improvised bombs of small power	Armed assaults / theft in vehicles or locations of money storage or counting	Sabotage	Riots	Kidnapping / hostage of company personnel and/or passengers	Seizure of vehicle or installation / station	Obstruction of transportation operation	Kidnapping of company key personnel	Seizure of vehicle / hostage of passengers following pursuit by the police	Homicide	Theft / robbery	Smuggling	Gang brawl	Injuries	Spoilage / incendiary		
Threat	Anti-social behaviour				Demonstrations / public gatherings / strikes that turn violent				Environmental accidents		Technological accidents			Transportation accidents				
Incident	Spoilage of foreign property	Vandalism	Suicide	Affray of sports followers or other groups	Hoaxes - threats	Seizure of installations / stations / movable assets	Obstruction of access	Spoilage / vandalism / incendiary	Air pollution	Ground pollution	Urban fires of large extent	Failure in electrical power network	Failure in power network	Failure in communications network	Failure in water supply	Rail accident / collision	Plane crash	Metro accidents
Threat	Collapse of infrastructure due to:					Technological intrusion								Abandoned objects (usual)		Abandoned objects (hazardous)		
Incident	Natural disaster or fire	Construction error	Failure to comply with safety rules	Insufficient / inappropriate infrastructure	Human error	Intentional damage	Unauthorized access / entrance in controlled areas	Unauthorized alteration of data	Communications interception	Communications interference	Technological viruses	Networks failure	Power shortage					
Threat	Other				Panic without important cause	Panic due to emergency	Natural disasters					Fires					Wildfires	
Incident	Absence of personnel	Fatigue / illness of personnel	Failure of equipment	Insufficient resources			Extreme weather effects	Geological effects: earthquakes, landslides	Hydro-geological effects	Biological: epidemic, invasion of insects and / rodents	In administration buildings	In movable assets	In stations	In depots	In parking areas	In stations surroundings		

1.3.1 Cyberwatching.eu

Cyberwatching.eu⁶ is the European observatory of research and innovation in the field of cybersecurity and privacy. Funded under the European Commission's H2020 programme, this brand-new project will contribute to making the Digital Single Market a safer place by promoting the uptake and understanding of cutting-edge cybersecurity and privacy services which emerge from Research and Innovation initiatives across Europe.

First to benefit are SMEs who will have unlimited access to project information and also to a Marketplace of new services to help improve their cybersecurity offering. In its mission to democratise cybersecurity for all, the project directly responds to the objectives of the recently signed contractual Public-Private Partnership on cybersecurity (c-PPP) which could become the reference framework for research and innovation initiatives across Europe. As the online hub for research and innovation in cybersecurity & privacy in Europe, the Cyberwatching.eu website offers European citizens a single gateway to innovative and trustworthy ICT products, services and software which take fundamental rights, such as privacy, into consideration.

One of the objectives of the Cyberwatching.eu project is to support projects in the cybersecurity domain in classifying and clustering themselves and others into meaningful groups of common topics and concerns to generate synergies and collaboration. The process by which this is achieved involves a two-tier taxonomy of cybersecurity topics, against which European projects, both national and international, are first mapped against the first tier of domains of cybersecurity. Since many projects concern themselves with not only one domain, the three domains in the first tier are ranked accordance to the level of concern in the mapped project: High, medium, low, or not applicable. As a consequence, some projects are entirely out of scope, as the only concern themselves with using cybersecurity procedures or technology instead of addressing any of them as a concern of its own right.

A **taxonomy of cybersecurity** has been defined, to allow a single uniform understanding of the different sub areas of cybersecurity R&I to be established. This will be a two-layer design, firstly a top-level set of three domains and then a subset of 6 areas which are individually indivisible. The taxonomy as developed within Cyberwatching.eu is intended to allow the identification of different aspects of cybersecurity and from this the way that different projects and activities concentrate on different sub areas in their developments.

The high-level definitions created are the following;

- Foundational technical methods & risk management for trustworthy systems in cybersecurity and privacy: The development of technologies that are directly associated with cybersecurity capabilities or features and methods by which the confidence in the technical capabilities of a system may be validated.
- Applications and user-oriented services to support cybersecurity and privacy: Specific capabilities or services which directly interact with system users and are developed with capabilities that are directly about how to improve the inherent capabilities and user experiences of cybersecurity and privacy in consumed services.
- Policy, governance, ethics, trust, and usability, human aspects of cyber security & privacy: Aspects of cyber security that are overwhelmingly driven by the human interaction, understanding and dependency on how secure systems are or have been designed to be.

Below these top-level domains are further subdivisions which look at the main areas, which then cover what we would consider the whole landscape:

- Secure systems and technology: How security can be built into technology from the design stage including cloud computing security, cryptography, trusted platforms, wireless security, mobile security and secure coding paradigms.
- Verification and assurance: Two disciplines that help establish how much confidence you can have in a system, both in terms of security and the privacy of all stakeholder groups who act with or in a system. Assurance focuses on managing risks related to the use, processing, storage, and transmission of information, whereas formal verification seeks to build a mathematical model of a digital system and then try to prove whether it is 'correct', often helping to find subtle flaws.
- Operational risk, management and analytics: Understanding the risk and harm resulting from cyberattacks, and how it propagates across and between organisations. Work focuses on creating situational awareness through aiming for a complete understanding of scenario and risk management;

⁶ <https://cyberwatching.eu/>

metrics and models for security postures; and analytics for predicting risk, prioritising responses and supporting security operations.

- Identity, behaviour, ethics and Privacy: Bringing diverse perspectives and interpretations to questions such as: Who are you online, how do you communicate, and what can (or should) you do? This also connects to the ongoing activities on Privacy launched through directives and regulations over the past year.
- National and international security, privacy and governance: looking at politics, international relations, defence, policy and governance issues: how do countries and communities interact with (and through) technology, and how might this change in different contexts?
- Human aspects of cyber security: Understanding the ways humans interact with (and through) digital systems – whether to understand and design for target users, or to understand how adversaries operate and can exploit the systems. This includes aspects like usability, trust, collaborative practices, social embeddedness, nationhood, cultural diversity, impact on economy, and the relationship between microsocial interactions and global structures [25].

1.3.2 SDN-MICROSENSE Project

The smart energy ecosystem constitutes the next technological leap of the conventional electrical grid, providing multiple benefits such as increased reliability, better service quality and efficient utilization of the existing infrastructures. However, despite the fact that it brings beneficial environmental, economic and social changes, it also generates significant security and privacy challenges, as it includes a combination of heterogeneous, co-existing smart and legacy technologies. Based on this reality, the SDN-microSENSE⁷ project intends to provide a set of secure, privacy-enabled and resilient to cyberattacks tools, thus ensuring the normal operation of EPES as well as the integrity and the confidentiality of communications. In particular, adopting an SDN-based technology, SDN-microSENSE will develop a three-layer security architecture, by deploying and implementing risk assessment processes, self-healing capabilities, large-scale distributed detection and prevention mechanisms, as well as an overlay privacy protection framework. Firstly, the risk assessment framework will identify the risk level of each component of EPES, identifying the possible threats and vulnerabilities. Accordingly, in the context of self-healing, islanding schemes and energy management processes will be deployed, isolating the critical parts of the network in the case of emergency. Furthermore, collaborative intrusion detection tools will be capable of detecting and preventing possible threats and anomalies timely. Finally, an incident repository will be designed to provide and share information to all parties involved and the Differential Privacy anonymisation technique is used to ensure data privacy. In the context of SDN-microSENSE projects several taxonomies, frameworks and tools in the energy domain have been developed.

1.3.2.1 SDN-microSENSE Risk Assessment Framework(S-RAF)

Risk management is the process of identifying, analysing and then responding to any risk that arises over the life cycle of any business operation and can potentially harm the output of that operation and any other related operation. Risk assessment is operating while the business is already in place and the development phase has been completed. There are multiple risk assessment metrics which can be calculated (Figure 11), however for the scope of the SDN-microSENSE project our main concern is cyber security risk assessment and the harm of the Electrical Power and Energy System (EPES) infrastructure concerning the cyber security risk [26].

⁷ <https://www.sdnmicrosense.eu/>

Figure 11: Risk Calculation Impact Categories

1.3.3 SPARTA Project

SPARTA⁸ (H2020-SU-ICT-2018-2020) is a novel Cybersecurity Competence Network, supported by Europe’s H2020 program, with the objective to develop and implement top-tier research and innovation cooperative actions. Strongly guided by concrete challenges forming an ambitious Cybersecurity Research & Innovation Roadmap, SPARTA will setup unique collaboration means, leading the way in building transformative capabilities and forming a world-leading Joint Competence Centre Infrastructure. From basic human needs (health) to economic activities (energy, finance, and transport) to technologies (ICT and industry) to sovereignty (eGovernment, public administration), four research and innovation Programs will push the boundaries to deliver advanced solutions to cover emerging challenges.

The SPARTA consortium, led by CEA, assembles a balanced set of 44 actors at the intersection of scientific excellence, technological innovation, and societal sciences in cybersecurity. Together, along with SPARTA Associates, they aim at re-thinking the way cybersecurity research, innovation, and training are performed in Europe across domains and expertise, from foundations to applications, in academia and industry. In sharing experiences and excellence, challenges and capabilities, SPARTA aims at making decisive contributions to the objective of European strategic autonomy.

In SPARTA, CAPE program that stands for Continuous assessment in polymorphous environments. This scientific activity of the SPARTA project addresses the issue of assessing cybersecurity performance of two environments, addressing security and safety co-design on one hand, complex software systems of systems on the other hand.

To define the security requirements a Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) must be performed but also having into account the Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment (HARA).

Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA): To detect all the vulnerabilities and potential threats of the system, it is appropriate to use vulnerability and threat analyses. In the CCCC vertical a Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) analysis has been elaborated to identify threats and assess the risks. Identifying them, allows valuable resources to be applied to the highest risk potential threats. The risk assessment component of a TARA considers the severity of the possible outcomes on the system and the likelihood that a potential attack can successfully be carried out, referred to as the attack potential. Focusing on the highest risk potential threats, the TARA helps to assign the most valuable cybersecurity controls during the application of more analysis techniques.

Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment (HARA): a Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment analysis has been developed in terms of security. The output of the HARA are the rated Hazards that will serve as root events for safety analysis and the Safety Goals that will be refined into more detailed safety requirements. The result

⁸ <https://www.sparta.eu/>

of this HARA analysis for the Connected & Cooperative Car Cybersecurity (CCCC) vertical, contains valuable knowledge to use for threat modelling and therefore, also for penetration testing. We considered until now five main hazards [27]:

- Erroneous Communication
- Loss of Communication
- Loss of Braking System
- Unintended Acceleration
- Unintended Steering

1.3.4 SHIELD Project

SHIELD⁹ (H2020-DS-2016-2017) project will unlock the value of health data to European citizens and businesses by overcoming security and regulatory challenges that today prevent this data being exchanged with those who need it. This will make it possible to provide better health care to mobile citizens across European borders and facilitate legitimate commercial uses of health data.

SHIELD case studies will address cross border scenarios in which a citizen needs health care while in one Member State, and care givers need access to their health data from different Member States. SHIELD will also consider how commercial providers of lifestyle services or wearable sensors may be involved in such data exchanges. SHIELD will thereby also create opportunities for using health data to create such products and services addressing the common European market.

SHIELD will provide guidance in best practice to achieve end-to-end security and data protection compliance in health and health related applications. SHIELD will also feed into CEN-Cenelec and ETSI efforts to create EU standards for data protection by design in eHealth.

In SHIELD, a taxonomy based on ISO 27005¹⁰ has been developed. The SHIELD knowledge base has incorporated support for evaluating risk levels using the procedures defined by ISO 27005. This was developed in the H2020 Rest Assured project, and was integrated into the SHIELD privacy by design risk modelling tools and knowledge base in late 2018. The knowledge base introduced as part of D4.1 covered basic security threats that would apply in any situation involving computer networks. They are not specific to SHIELD but still very relevant as they might compromise the system. Some changes were also needed to incorporate SHIELD control strategies, even though the threat itself is not SHIELD-specific. Furthermore, an appendix explaining the use of words such as “threat”, “trustworthiness”, “control”, etc within the System Security Modeller and the associated knowledge base have been provided.

Further details can be consulted in [28].

1.3.5 PDP4E Project

PDP4E¹¹ (H2020-DS-2016-2017) is an innovation action that will provide software and system engineers with methods and software tools to systematically apply data protection principles in the projects they carry out, so that the products they create comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), thus bringing the principles of Privacy and Data Protection by Design to practice. PDP4E will integrate privacy and data protection engineering functionalities into existent, mainstream software tools that are already in use by engineers, focusing on open-source tools that will be integrated in the Eclipse ecosystem, The approach will integrate methods proposed by the privacy engineering community (e.g. LINDDUN, ISO/IEC 27550 Privacy engineering), and the industry of software and system engineering tools (e.g. MUSE, PAPHYRUS or OpenCert) using a model driven engineering approach. PDP4E will introduce privacy and data protection into software and system engineering disciplines (Risk Management, Requirements Engineering, Model-Driven Design, and Assurance), which drive the everyday activities of engineers. Results of PDP4E will be assessed by two demonstration pilots on industries where privacy and data protection are especially relevant, one on novel financial applications and services (fintech application domain) and one on big data on smart grid (smart grid

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/727301/>

¹⁰ <https://www.iso27001security.com/html/27005.html>

¹¹ <https://www.pdp4e-project.eu/>

application domain). PDP4E will promote its results in engineering communities, as Eclipse (community of software developers) or IPEN (community of stakeholders with an interest on privacy engineering). An open Alliance for Privacy and Data Protection Engineering is planned as a follow-up of the project, building on that community and the synergies among partners.

In the context of PDP4E project, LINDDUN, a privacy threat modeling methodology that helps software engineers with limited privacy expertise to introduce privacy early on in the software development lifecycle has been provided. LINDDUN is a model-based approach that leverages a data flow diagram (DFD) as representation of the system to be analyzed. This DFD will serve as basis for the analysis, as each of its elements is systematically examined thoroughly for privacy threats. The methodology is also knowledge-based. It provides an overview of the most common attack paths associated with the set of privacy threat categories contained in the acronym LINDDUN (Linkability, Identifiability, Non-repudiation, Detectability, Disclosure of information, Unawareness, Non-compliance). The attack paths are represented as threat trees that detail possible causes of threats.

LINDDUN privacy threat tree catalog provides assistance in discovering threats. A detailed description of the threat category in general has been provided. Figure 12 shows an example of such threat description:

Figure 12: Example of improved general threat description: Linkability
Further details can be consulted in [29]

1.3.6 CORE Project

CORE¹² project consolidates, amplifies, extends and demonstrates EU knowledge and capabilities and international co-operation for securing supply chains whilst maintaining or improving business performance, with specific reference to key Supply Chain Corridors. CORE has been driven by the requirements of:

- The Customs, law enforcement authorities, and other agencies nationally and internationally to increase effectiveness of security & trade compliance, without increasing the transaction costs for business and to increase co-operative security risk management (supervision & control).
- The business communities, specifically shippers, forwarders, terminal operators, carriers and financial stakeholders to integrate compliance and trade facilitation concepts like green lanes and pre-clearance with supply chain visibility and optimisation.

CORE consolidates solutions developed in Reference Projects in each supply chain sector (port, container, air, post). Implementation-driven R&D is then undertaken designed to discover gaps and practical problems and to develop capabilities and solutions that could deliver sizable and sustainable progress in supply chain security across all EU Member States and on a global scale.

In the context of CORE project, a taxonomy related to the supply chain risk domain has been developed providing a high-level identification of threats to supply chains.

¹² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/603993>

The project utilizes a similar concept for threats as PRECINCT, recognising three kinds of threats for supply chain CIs:

- I. Environmental Threats
- II. Terrorism & Crime Threats
- III. Supply Chain Operational Risks

Threat severity/impact is assessed with the PEAR method, meaning each threat's impact is considered for:

- I. People
- II. Environment
- III. Assets
- IV. Reputation

1.3.7 PRECINCT Threat Taxonomy

For the elaboration of the PRECINCT taxonomy, different sources have been analysed [30][31][32][33][34][35][36][37][38][39][40]. The main aim has been to provide a list of threats that fully covers the current context in the PRECINCT project and mainly in the LLs.

The categories of hazards and threats that have been provided and shown in Table 14 are the following:

- Technology related accidents
- Natech related accidents
- Physical attack
- Cyber attack

Table 14: PRECINCT categories of hazards and threats

#	Categories of Hazards and Threats	Sub-category (phenomena)	Principal aspect	Explanations
1	Technology related accidents	1.1 Process usets (process parameter deviations)	Safety	Non-intentional events in industrial site/facility due to technology related presence of the hazardous substances or energies being released. Usually resulting in fires, explosions, toxic releases to the environmental media. Should include nuclear and radiological events. Events are usually triggered by the deficiencies in the human-tehnology-organization (HTO) system.
		1.2 Spontaneous chemical reaction		
		1.3 Containment failures (pipes, tanks, vessels, containers, hoses, gaskets, etc.)		
		1.4 Equipment malfunctions (pumps, valves, instruments, sensors, logical solvers, actuators, interlocks)		
		1.5 Loss of utilities (electricity, intertization, water, refrigeration, air, heat, steam, transfer fluids, ventilation)		
		1.6 Human errors (errors, slips and lapses in design, construction, operations, maintenance, testing and inspection)		
		1.7 Management systems failure (e.g., safety management system ineffective)		
2	Natech related accidents	2.1 Geological (earthquake, tsunami, volcanic eruption, landslide, mudslide, debris flow, frost heave, rock fall, avalanche, soil erosion)	Safety	Non-intentional events started by the natural hazards/extereme phenomena triggering technological accidents through deficiencies in HTO measures. Closely related to the category #1 above.
		2.2 Hydro-meteorological - weather hurricane, tornado, wind, ice storm, hail)		
		2.3 Hydro-meteorological - lightning		
		2.4 Hydro-meteorological - floods (storm surge, flooding, washout)		
		2.5 Hydro-meteorological - extreme temperatures (frost, cold weather, hot weather, drought, wild fire) and Space (solar flare - coronal mass ejection and electromagnetic radiation)		
		2.6 Environment threats (e.g. pollution; climate change)		
3	Physical attack	3.1 Unauthorized physical access	Security	Intentional events in industrial site/facility caused by human factor. Usually resulting unautherized acces to critical site or physical attack on critical site.
		3.2 Terrorism/Bombings attacks		
		3.3 Information leak/Sharing		
		3.4 Vadnalism/Sabotage		
		3.5 Theft		
4	Cyber attack	4.1 Eavesdropping/Interception/ Hijacking (Intercepting compromising emissions, Interception of information, Interfering radiation, Replay of messages, Network Reconnaissance and Information gathering, Man in the middle/ Session hijacking.....)	Security	An event or condition that has the potential for causing asset loss and the undesirable consequences or impact from such loss. Note: The specific causes of asset loss, and for which the consequences of asset loss are assessed, can arise from a variety of conditions and events related to adversity, typically referred to as disruptions, hazards, or threats. Regardless of the specific term used, the basis of asset loss constitutes all forms of intentional, unintentional, accidental, incidental, misuse, abuse, error, weakness, defect, fault, and/or failure events and associated conditions.
		4.2 Nefarious Activity/ Abuse (Identity theft, Unsolicited E-mail, Denial of service, Malicious code/ software/ activity, Social Engineering, Abuse of Information Leakage, Generation and use of rogue certificates, Targeted attacks (APTs etc.))	Security	

2 CIP Measures and Systems

Providing security is one of the central concerns of any society. There is no policy area without a crucial component of security. A safe and secure environment is the very basis on which any stable society is founded upon. A competitive EU based security industry offering solutions for enhanced security can make a substantial contribution to the resilience of European society [48].

According to a “Study on the Competitiveness on the EU security industry” performed by Ecorys Research and Consulting on the EU security industry on behalf of the European Commission, a general distinction between two different security threat categories has been performed:

- **Traditional security**, corresponding to protection against (‘endogenous’) threats such as ‘ordinary’ criminal activity, fire protection, etc.
- **New security** corresponds to protection against (‘exogenous’) threats such as terrorism, organised crime, cyber-crime, etc. and also including protection against and response to major catastrophic events [49].

It is necessary to deal with the CIP issues as a complex system because with critical infrastructure protection (as well as with security in general) it applies that a system is as strong as its weakest link. This means that the individual measures for CIP (the ways of protecting the CI) must be balanced, intertwined and complementary.

A risk and crisis management approach constitutes a systematic process to manage risk and it is fundamental to incorporate it in the daily strategy. Nowadays, every society is exposed to a great amount of a variety of risks and threats, dealing with IT security is an imperative, the measures for critical infrastructure protection are based on a complex approach to security that includes both risk management and physical protection actions.

The basic measures for CI protection are

- **Risk and crisis management:** A risk and crisis management approach constitutes a systematic process to manage risk and it is fundamental to incorporate it in the daily strategy. The strategy consists of five phases representing the necessary scope of process-based risk and crisis management. The five phases are:
 - 1. Preliminary planning to establish a system of risk and crisis management.
 - 2. Risk analysis.
 - 3. Specification of preventive measures.
 - 4. Implementation of a crisis management system.
 - 5. Regular evaluation of the previous phases.
- **Business continuity planning:** defined as a series of activities focused on decreasing the risk of collision emergence and restricting impacts on critical processes. It is not only a plan of a response to a critical event but also includes an important aspect of prevention.
- **IT Security:** the main elements/parts of the IT security are to set up a set of rules and requirements to ensure the protection and security of information; management of physical access to ensure that only the personnel could access to critical information; set up an authentication and authorization process; a Security supervision and management system; implementing antivirus solutions and protection for the web (firewall, IDS/IPS sensor, content filters, antispam and antivirus protection); adopt a data encryption system; and protecting mobile devices.
- **Physical protection** of any object (building, appliance, object etc.) is achieved by combining and intertwining of three basic elements: physical protection systems, response team/activity, regime protection.
 - Physical protection systems that include:
 - Mechanical barrier systems in object concepts as the building are walls, roofs, floors, doors and windows objects. Generally, these are for example: safety locks, grilles, security film, security and toughened laminated glass, safe, safety deposit boxes.

- Technical protection systems are: Intruder and/or Hold-up Alarm System (HAS); Security Camera System (CCTV system, CCTV surveillance system); Fire alarm system (FAS); Access Control System (ACS); Mechatronics System.
 - Response team/activity: carried out by own resources, security, private security service employees or by police or army. The core is a response of a human element to danger/security disruption/object protection such as breaking in, technological breakdown etc.
 - Regime protection/measure: administrative and organization measures for securing protected interests and values. This includes checking the entrance of employees, clients, visitors; property protection against theft, damage; continuity and security of operation.
- **Personal and administrative security** intended as the determination and subsequent documentation of security roles and responsibilities according to requirements of the company security policy. In order to ensure an adequate level of security, it is necessary to carry out inspections with the new employees [50].

For a classification of the security products, the Ecorys report on Security Regulation, Conformity Assessment & Certification, classifies security products into two main categories, depending on familiarity of operation and function:

- **General purpose security products (Type-1):** security products and solutions aimed at addressing 'familiar' security situations (security threats or functions) through the application of improved but existing technology. This includes what may loosely be called 'traditional' security equipment (e.g. intruder detection, CCTV, access control, security barriers).
- **Priority and sensitive security products (Type-2):** security products and solutions addressing 'unfamiliar' or new types of threats that often require the development or application of new technologies and approaches. This latter category may be extended to changes in organisation and implementation of security functions; for example through the automatisisation of security functions. This includes what may loosely be called 'new' security equipment (i.e. corresponding to products/technologies developed primarily to address threats such as terrorism, organised crime, cyber-crime, etc.) [51].

In general, critical infrastructure protection methodologies, models and simulations are used to understand infrastructure systems, their interdependencies, vulnerabilities, impacts of potential failures and their propagation across interdependent infrastructure systems, based on risk assessments of all the involved critical infrastructures. They may also be used to support performance measurement, conceptual design, impact evaluation, response planning, vulnerability analyses and economic impact assessments.

Another classification of critical infrastructure protection tools is based on their purpose, namely their functionality as follow:

- Risk identification.
- Risk assessment.
- Risk prioritization.
- Risk mitigation planning.
- Effectiveness evaluation.

This approach follows risk assessment purposes, so it is also linked to the fundamental role of risk management.

According to the National Infrastructure Protection Plan (NIPP)¹³, tools, frameworks, and methodologies are classified according to the purpose that they serve, i.e. the stage of the risk management framework that they aid with their output. In Figure 13, the classification of the 68 tools according to the risk management purpose is shown. This represents a review of the capabilities of various not only strategies and applications, but also methodologies which are used for both identification and evaluation or risks that occur in critical

¹³ <https://www.cisa.gov/national-infrastructure-protection-plan>

infrastructure. Tools that lie deeper than others in the same branch support additional risk analysis purposes [52].

Figure 13: CIP tools classification according to risk management purpose

There is not a unique approach to protect critical infrastructures, but there is always great necessity of interdependencies analysis in order to understand the interconnections which exist between multiple critical infrastructures.

2.1 CIP Measures and Systems in Existing EU Projects

EU programme¹⁴ has funded over 100 critical infrastructure protection projects from 2007 onwards. These projects focused on a variety of issues including national and European information sharing and alerting systems, the development of ways to assess interdependence between electronic and electricity transmission networks, and the creation of a 'good practice' manual for policy makers. The EU programme is designed to protect citizens and critical infrastructures from terrorist attacks and other security incidents by fostering prevention and preparedness, namely by improving the protection of critical infrastructures and addressing crisis management. A Europe-wide approach helps manage the risks across the EU. Reducing the vulnerabilities of critical infrastructure and increasing their resilience is one of the major objectives of the EU. An adequate level of protection must be ensured and the detrimental effects of disruptions on the society and citizens must be limited as far as possible. EU-funded security projects were reviewed with the aim of examining current attempts at categorisations of CIP measures, products and systems in order to provide building blocks for the PRECINCT project, and also to gather information on available security technologies and the needs that they help address. The projects were analysed with a view to examine the different ways in which security products can be categorised from these different angles.

2.1.1 ETTIS Project

The aim of the ETTIS¹⁵ – European Security trends and threats in society - project is a) to identify, understand and assess in a scenarios framework future threats, needs and opportunities for societal security, b) to develop and test a methodological approach and model for a revolving process of security research priority setting, c) to derive research priorities geared towards the needs of user organisations, as well as rationales and options for policy intervention, and d) to help increase awareness of and attention to security research results, and contribute to overcoming barriers by advancing and testing a range of intelligence tools and techniques. ETTIS relies on a comprehensive concept of security that encompasses both technological and non-technological opportunities as well as emerging security-related ethical, cultural and organisational challenges.

The ETTIS project draws attention to the fact that security is a concern at many different levels in contemporary society. The project categorises security into seven dimensions: physical security, political security, socio-economic security, cultural security, environmental security, radical uncertainty security and cyber security.

With regard to security solutions, ETTIS lists them in Table 15 [53]:

Table 15: ETTIS Technological Solutions

ETTIS Technological Solutions	
Information, intelligence, surveillance and monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tools for sharing and managing information ● Early warning systems, threat detection ● Comprehensive surveillance for monitoring of borders ● Sensors and facial recognition ● Event detection
Detection technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Robotic devices ● Sensors (fast working sensors, ease of use and mobile sensors)
CBRN and crisis preparedness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sensing and detecting CBRN substances ● Software and hardware tools supporting decision making in crises ● Reliable means of communication ● Indoor site navigation systems
Environment and radical uncertainty (including health)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Climate change related security efforts

¹⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/pages/page/critical-infrastructure_en

¹⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/285593>

Information and cyberspace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cryptographic techniques • Operating systems • Anomaly detection
Space	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weather monitoring • Surveillance satellites

2.1.2 CRISP Project

CRISP¹⁶ - Evaluation and Certification Schemes for Security Products – project aims at facilitating a harmonised playing field for the European security industry by developing a robust methodology for security product certification. CRISP focuses specifically on “security function” in its taxonomy and places security application areas as the starting point from which products and systems are then categorised. Within each or the security application areas, sub-areas are presented. Further categorising equipment and systems the security demands (level 2) and they form a category of key requirements which are necessary in the respective security application areas. Following the security demands are the security functions (level 3), a further categorisation based on the intended result within the application area and in order to implement the security demand. This classification is shown in Table 16:

Table 16: CRISP Security classification areas

Security Application Areas (Level 1)	Security Demands (Level 2)	Security Functions (Level 3)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Border security/management • Critical Infrastructure • Emergency Preparedness Centres/Crisis Management • Security of the citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access control • Asset/freight/cargo security • Cyber security • Employee/visitor safety • Loss prevention/shrinkage • Perimeter/area/building security • Point of transaction • Situation awareness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess • Authorise • Communicate • Control • Create situational awareness • Detain • Identify • Information collection, storage and management to produce intelligence • Locate • Prevent/protect • Track • Verify

Finally on the last level of the CRISP taxonomy, the relevant security products and systems corresponding to the three previous levels of application area, security demand and security function have been listed. The following Figure 14 and Figure 15 are related to the Critical Infrastructure area [54]:

¹⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/607941>

Figure 14: CRISP project - CI security applications' taxonomy (a)

Figure 15: CRISP project - CI security applications' taxonomy (b)

2.1.3 SCOUT Project

The SCOUT¹⁷ Project - Multitech SeCurty system for intercOnnected space control groUnd staTions - is a capability project developed under FP7 funding programme in response to the Call SEC-2013.2.2-5 (From

¹⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/607019/reporting/it>

2014-11-01 to 2018-04-30). The main objective is to provide significant improvement in the security and resilience of complex interconnected space control ground station networks. The project analyses in an innovative way the vulnerabilities of the different parts of the space control ground station network and provides state of the art tools and innovative solution in order to limit the impact of accidents/attacks. The goal of the project is to study, design and analyse on a risk-based approach, a security system relying on multiple innovative and low impact technologies for the protection of space control ground stations and the satellite links against physical and cyber-attacks, and for intelligent reconfiguration of the ground station network in case of failure.

The SCOUT system implements three main security functionalities for physical attack protection; for cyber-attack detection and countermeasures; and for automatic restoration and reconfiguration of the space control ground station network. The SCOUT system is composed of three different subsystems:

- **SENSNET subsystem**

A scalable distributed multisensor network for protection against physical attacks, which is composed of low impact sensor, namely passive sensors (passive radar, infrared camera, radiometric radar) and low emission radars (noise radar-based sensors - NRBS).

- **CYBERSENS subsystem**

A distributed telecommunication network sensing system, for the detection and protection against cyber-attacks, composed of several network probes (monitoring devices located at every ground station), host probes (lightweight software sensing agents residing in the actual ground station machines), a honeynet (a decoy network used to detect, and track cyberattacks), and a central engine which coordinates the entire infrastructure.

- **RECOVER subsystem**

A management network system for automatic restoration and intelligence reconfiguration of the space control ground station network, designed in accordance with the distributed Smart Sensor Network paradigm, where the reconfiguration and control are governed by distributed logic.

The first two subsystems (SENSNET and CYBERSENS) allow for the acquisition of information about potential attacks of the ground station and/or possible damages of attacks once inflicted. These data are processed to have a situation awareness picture, which is used to assess the degree of alert. The SENSET and CYBERSENS are suitably controlled to focus their resources on potential threats. CYBERSENS provides a “response engine” to mitigate the effects of cyber-attacks combined with RECOVER system. According to the result of the assessment, the RECOVER system is activated.

The following Table 17 shows the main tools:

Table 17: SCOUT project's tools

Focus: space control ground stations network, in particular those used by earth observation and satellite navigation systems, and secure communication links to satellites	
Detection and protection against physical and cyber attacks	<p>Risk analysis tools for the acquisition of information about potential attacks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Physical attacks (multi-sensor network for protection against physical attacks) ● Cyber-attacks (distributed telecommunication network sensing system, for the detection and protection against cyber-attacks) <p>In order to have a situation awareness picture, which is used to assess the degree of alert.</p>
Mitigation and response engine for automatic restoration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mitigation and response engine to mitigate the effects of cyber-attacks. ● Management network system for automatic restoration and intelligence reconfiguration of a space control ground station network

2.1.4 PROGRESS Project

PROGRESS¹⁸ - Protection & Resilience Of Ground Based infRAstructures for European Space Systems - is a project co-funded by the European Union under the FP7 funding programme in response to the SEC-2013.2.2-5 call (From 2014-05-01 to 2017-10-31). PROGRESS focuses on improving the security and resilience of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) and its results are also applicable to other space systems, including telecommunications and earth observation. PROGRESS focuses on the detection and mitigation of intrusions to GNSS. The ultimate goal is to enable expanded intelligence in GNSS architectures so as to ensure uninterrupted performance of services. The potential impact of attacks will be reduced through protective solutions, attacks will be detected and analysed for impact and where necessary affected elements of the GNSS will be reconfigured.

The prioritisation of threats and scenarios is used as input to develop a prototype Security Management Solution (SMS), a centralized solution able to automatically detect malicious actions with a built-in reconfiguration capability allowing to ensure the overall system Quality of Service (QoS). PROGRESS SMS is composed of an Integrated Ground Station Security Monitoring System (IGSSMS) and a Security Control Centre (SCC). The IGSSMS is an innovative monitoring solution for the detection of cyber-attacks, Radiofrequency (RF) attacks and physical attacks. The Security Control Centre analyses the impact of the reported disturbances on the system performance and Quality of Service and proposes mitigation strategies, including automatic system reconfiguration.

The following Table 18 shows the main tools:

Table 18: PROGRESS project' main tools

Focus: Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) and its results are also applicable to other space systems, including telecommunications and earth observation.	
Risk Assessment methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A holistic methodology enabling assessment of threat scenarios on GNSS, including the potential impact on society.
Detection and protection against physical, RF and cyber attacks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated Ground Station Security Monitoring System (IGSSMS), an innovative monitoring solution for the detection of cyber-attacks, Radiofrequency (RF) attacks and physical attacks. • Detection solutions for: cyber-attacks (Denial of Service (DOS) attacks and spoofing); Radio Frequency (RF) interference (jamming and spoofing) detection and localization and physical attacks (explosive, and High Powered Microwave (HPM)).
Impact Analysis Mitigation and response engine for automatic restoration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security Control Center (SCC) analyses the impact of the reported disturbances on the system performance and Quality of Service (QoS) and proposes mitigation strategies, including automatic system reconfiguration.

2.1.5 ATENA Project

ATENA¹⁹ - Advanced Tools to assEss and mitigate the criticality of ICT compoNents and their dependencies over Critical InfrAstructures - project funded under the H2020 framework programme in response to the DS-03-2015 call (From 2016-05-01 to 2019-04-30). Over recent years, Industrial and Automation Control Systems (IACS) adopted in Critical Infrastructures (CIs) have become more complex due to the increasing number of interconnected devices, and to the large amount of information exchanged among system components. ATENA project, with reference to the above-mentioned interdependent scenario, aims at achieving the desired level of Security and Resilience of the considered CIs, while preserving their efficient and flexible

¹⁸ <http://www.progress-satellite.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/700581/it>

management against a wide variety of cyber-physical threats, being those malicious attacks or unexpected faults, which may affect IACS, corporate networks or single devices. The design and development of ATENA platform is driven by the security needs of energy and water domains. In particular, ATENA develops a Software Defined Security paradigm combining new anomaly detection algorithms and risk assessment methodologies within a distributed environment and provides a suite of integrated market-ready ICT networked components and advanced tools embedding innovative algorithms both for correct static CI configuration and for fast dynamic CI reaction in presence of adverse events.

In order to understand CI behaviour, identify their vulnerability and protect them against increasing level of cybercrime, a Unified Modelling Framework is really helpful and challenging at the same time. A Unified Modelling Framework with ad-hoc models to control physical flow efficiency and improve resilience across CIs against threats. The ATENA project uses such a framework for assessing CI flow efficiency, robustness, reconfiguration and resilience under cyber-physical threats aiming at increasing CI operators and customers awareness, providing real time optimization of CI flows at different (national, regional, urban) levels. Moreover, ATENA defines dynamic security paradigms for resilience of Cyber-Physical systems. CIs are increasingly being controlled by ICT networked objects and are becoming Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) where industrial Ethernet based on IP protocol is widely adopted. ATENA develops a suite of integrated ICT networked components for detection and reaction in presence of adverse events in industrial distributed systems.

The following Table 19 shows the main tools:

Table 19: ATENA project's main tools

Focus: Energy and water domains	
Anomaly Detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New anomaly detection algorithms and risk assessment methodologies within a distributed ICT-controlled CI environment. • A suite of ICT networked components for detection and reaction in presence of adverse events in distributed CIs. In particular, a distributed Intrusion Detection System (IDS) will help in identifying new and unknown attacks affecting the system.
Mitigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methodologies and technologies for increasing auto-reconfiguring capability of ICT-controlled CIs when a fault or an attack affects their functionalities. • This resilience-related capability tries to extend the standard security approaches based on perimeter defence by introducing the concept of Dynamic Reconfiguration of Security Mechanisms and Relocation of Security Functions as a consequence of detected attacks and taking into account the current operations in the CI.
Vulnerability assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ATENA develops a formalization of the steps between the detection of a cyber-event and the evaluation of the risk associated to the failure of a component, and then, to the failure of the entire CI. This kind of vulnerability assessment has to take into account the problems related to the interdependent nature of all CIs.

2.1.6 SAURON Project

SAURON²⁰ project - Scalable multidimensional situation awareness solution for protecting European ports - , funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic CIP-01-2016-2017 (From 2017-05-01 to 2020-04-30) and puts the focus on protection of EU Ports under Transport Infrastructure and means of transportation type of CI. Security threats in ports increasingly come not only in physical form but also as cyber-attacks on critical communications systems. SAURON project proposes the holistic situation awareness concept as an

²⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/740477/it>

integrated, scalable and yet installation-specific solution for protecting EU ports and its surroundings. The vision of SAURON is to provide a multidimensional yet installation-specific Situational Awareness (SA) platform to help port operators anticipate and withstand potential cyber, physical or combined threats to their freight and cargo business and to the safety of their employees, visitors, passengers and citizens in the vicinity.

SAURON solution combines the more advanced physical security features with the newest techniques in prevention, detection and mitigation of cyber-threats, including synthetic cyberspace aspects through the use of new visualization techniques such as immersive interfaces and cyber 3D models. In addition, a Hybrid Situation Awareness (HSA) application capable of determining the potential consequences of any threat shows the potential cascading effect of a detected threat both in the physical and cyber domains. SAURON can be used to engage with the public in surrounding areas and rescue/security teams that will be able to communicate any potential event or situation that could put their safety at risk. Reducing the vulnerabilities of EU ports, as one of the main European critical infrastructures and increasing their systemic resilience in the face of a physical, cyber or combined threat is also part of the SAURON main objective.

The following Table 20 shows the main tools:

Table 20: SAURON project's main tools

Focus: protection of EU Ports under Transport Infrastructure and means of transportation type of CI.	
Detection of physical and cyber threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A complete physical SA (PSA) system which includes novel features such as dynamic location of resources and assets, location, management and monitoring of sensors, including cameras mounted on drones, security perimeter control, robust and secure tactical communication network and so on. • An advanced and scalable cyber SA (CSA) system capable of preventing and detecting threats and in case of a declared attack, capable of mitigating the effects of the infection/intrusion. This CSA system will include new visualization paradigms for the cyber space. • The SAURON CSA application relies on a cyber-security monitoring platform that will be able to acquire, process and analyse information gathered from multiple sources. • On a real-time basis, different cyber security sensors are gathering the relevant information from these sources, processing the data in different cyber security incident detectors and sending possible incidents to a correlation engine.
Correlation engine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A correlation engine processes all the collected information and applies intelligent rules in order to identify the most relevant facts from all the data. The correlation engine will be able to generate intelligence to be disseminated to the operators of the system, in order for them to take decisions about the global cyber security state of the port. These advanced modules employ intelligent algorithms, based on techniques such as machine learning, to identify previously unknown attacks.
Global Situation Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Hybrid SA (HSA) system receiving both physical and cyber alarms on potential threats from the real world and the cyber space respectively. The HSA application shows the potential consequences/effects of these threats in the other planes including cascading effects. This innovative solution takes into account the real detected alarms of both applications and identifies and evaluates inter-correlations among different potential threats. This way once a real physical and/or cyber threat is detected the potential consequences

	including cascading effect in both planes (physical and cyber) will be automatically shown to the decisions makers in order to give them a holistic SA on what is happen and how the situation could evolve.
Decision Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The HSA proposes some decision support actions that could help the decision makers to prevent or even mitigate the future stated consequences.
Alert System and Response	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An Emergency Population Warning System, allowing local, regional, or national authorities to contact members of rescue/security teams and the public (also integrating Smart City Platforms (SCP)) in order to warn them and draw their attention to an immediate hazard. This will encourage them to take a specific action in response to an emergency event or threat.

2.1.7 STOP-IT Project

STOP-IT²¹ project - Strategic, Tactical, Operational Protection of water Infrastructure against cyber-physical Threats -, funded under H2020 programme and addresses the topic CIP-01-2016-2017 (From 2017-06-01 to 2021-05-31). Water critical infrastructures (CIs) are essential for human society, life and health and they can be endangered by physical/cyber threats with severe societal consequences. The STOP-IT project aims at finding solutions to protect critical water infrastructure against physical and cyber threats. STOP-IT will contribute to the human wellbeing and safety through reducing the impacts of both natural hazards and cyber-attacks in the water critical infrastructure analyzing current technologies and proposing new palliative actions. The project aims to ensure the resilience and safety of integrated water cycle systems in the face of cyber threats and intentional physical threats.

STOP-IT solutions are based on technologies that include mature technologies, like public warning systems and smart locks that are improved by their combination and embedment, and novel ones such as high-volume real-time sensor data protection via blockchain schemes or efficient water contamination detection algorithms. The Technological Center Eurecat will develop, within the STOP-IT consortium, high-tech tools to prevent cyber-attacks and natural hazards that could jeopardise water supply networks and vital infrastructure for cities. The STOP-IT integrated platform is scalable (scaling from small utilities to large ones), adaptable (including various modules addressing different needs, with expandability for future modules), and flexible (the water utility managers can decide how to use it and it will be usable by experts, novices, and even non-technical staff). It also supports strategic/tactical planning, real time operational decision making and post-action assessment for the key parts of the water infrastructure. Building on this solid basis, STOP-IT delivers high impact through the creation of hands-on training, best practice guidelines, support for certification and standardization as well as by fostering market opportunities, also leveraging the EU water technology platform's multi-stakeholder network. Within Communities of Practice (CoPs), STOP-IT provides space for an effective participation, communication and learning. The CoPs bring together relevant stakeholders and experts for given security issues, developing a common understanding of the advantages and disadvantages of various options for tackling different kinds of threats.

The following Table 21 shows the main tools:

Table 21: STOP-IT project's main tools

Focus: Water critical infrastructures	
Risk assessment and treatment framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A risk assessment and treatment framework forms the strategic and tactical decision making element of the overall risk management framework. Innovative solutions for risk treatment (prevention, detection, mitigation and recovery) of critical water infrastructures at the operational level.

²¹ <https://stop-it-project.eu/>

Detection and protection against physical and cyber threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toolbox of technologies for protection against physical threats, such as coordinated network cameras, XACML Authorization Engine, human presence detection using WiFi signals, water quality monitoring technologies for the early detection and impact minimization of contamination events (intentional attacks) and applications to service employees and to central management systems. • Cyber threat incident service • Real-time anomaly detection system
Alert System and Information Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communities of Practice (CoP) for water systems protection serves as a forum to encourage and facilitate information sharing, co-development and transferability amongst infrastructure operators, expert communities and other stakeholders. • A Public warning system allows the information sharing with the public in the areas affected by critical events and improved visualisation interfaces to facilitate the provision of a common operational picture for critical water infrastructure operators

2.1.8 SUCCESS Project

SUCCESS²² project - Securing Critical Energy Infrastructures -, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic DRS-12-2015 (From 2016-05-01 to 2018-10-3). The SUCCESS project develops an overarching approach to threat and countermeasure analysis with special focus on the vulnerabilities introduced by Smart Meters in the energy domain. The project aims at designing, developing and validating on small scale field trials a novel holistic adaptable security framework which is able to significantly reduce the risks of cyber threats and attacks when next generation, real-time, scalable, unbundled smart meters are deployed in smart electricity grids, enabling innovative applications and value-added services within the emerging smart decentralised energy system paradigm. SUCCESS is developing a new approach to the security of the energy systems, guaranteeing their security of operation. SUCCESS will achieve this objective by encapsulating the key challenges of Security, Resilience, Survivability and Privacy, as well as the implementation of Next Generation Open Real-time Smart Metering (NORM).

The following Table 22 shows the main tools:

Table 22: SUCCESS project's main tools

Focus: on the vulnerabilities introduced by Smart Meters in the energy domain	
Detection of threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SUCCESS Security Monitoring Solution to secure smart devices through the development of an unbundled Next-generation Open Real time smart Meter (NORM) and a decision support system for DSO, named DSO Security Monitoring Centre (DSOSMC), capable of detecting cyber-attacks on the distribution area of the grid and of applying a proper set of countermeasures from a set of designed reactive responses. • Threat modelling has been performed and techniques for identifying new, as yet unknown, threats have been developed, including the analysis of the potential physical and cyber threats related to the Smart Grid "Access Network".
Mitigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A countermeasure dashboard toolbox named DSOSMC (DSO Security Monitoring Centre) which determines the most appropriate set of countermeasures to be applied to the detected incidents and related threats impacting to the NaN level of the smart grid.
Resiliency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The resiliency by design technique explored in the SUCCESS project is mainly based on the cloud-computing paradigm. This mechanism is the base of the proposed Double Virtualization

²² <https://www.success-energy.eu/>

	technique, to increase system resiliency by exploiting cloud resources offered by the next generation breakout gateway (the so-called edge cloud).
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2.1.9 SmartResilience Project

SmartResilience²³ project - Smart Resilience Indicators for Smart Critical Infrastructures -, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic DRS-14-2015 (From 2016-05-01 to 2019-04-30). SmartResilience significantly improves the resilience of critical infrastructure, such as energy and water supply, transportation and information and communication grids etc., by providing a uniform and comprehensive methodology of risk and resilience assessment. SmartResilience provides solutions that are suitable to enhance the societal resilience in European countries and the organizational resilience among European infrastructure owners. Smart Resilience aims to provide an innovative “holistic” methodology for assessing resilience that is based on resilience indicators. Smart Resilience specific objectives are to identify existing indicators suitable for assessing resilience of smart critical infrastructures (SCIs); to identify new “smart” resilience indicators (RIs); to develop advanced resilience assessment methodology and tools and to test and validate the methodology/tools. Smart Resilience will significantly improve the resilience of SCIs by providing a uniform and comprehensive methodology of risk and resilient assessment. This assessment will lead to proactive innovations that eventually will raise the level of resilience at those SCIs.

SmartResilience develops a new advanced resilience assessment methodology based on a new set of smart Resilience Indicators that enable end-users (authorities, operators and owners of critical infrastructures) to better assess the resilience of the respective infrastructure, especially with respect to future and emerging threats, including those imposed by the enhancement and evolution of critical infrastructures towards “smartness”. This improved assessment methodology is supported by a model to identify interdependencies, between infrastructures as well as between these infrastructures and other sectors. The SmartResilience solutions is delivered in form of a practical guideline and a supporting tool (“SCI Dashboard”) for resilience assessment. SmartResilience is not only focused to technical aspects of resilience. The project covers security needs arising from disaster risks, including threats to life. The main planned results of SmartResilience are a Resilience Assessment Guideline and a tool (“Smart Critical Infrastructure Dashboard”), both aiming at supporting end-users (authorities, critical infrastructure operators and owners) in improving the disaster resilience of respective critical infrastructures through indicator-based assessment of their resilience capabilities. The solutions provided by SmartResilience are oriented towards practical needs of end-users and will be developed in close collaboration with all relevant stakeholders. A resilience management framework includes risk analysis as a central component. Risk analysis depends on characterization of the threats, vulnerabilities and consequences of adverse events to determine the expected loss of critical functionality.

The following Table 23 shows the main tools:

Table 23: SmartResilience project's main tools

Focus: Smart critical infrastructures (SCIs), such as energy & water supply, transportation and information and communication grids etc.	
Resilience Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identifying existing indicators suitable for assessing resilience of SCIs and new “smart” resilience indicators (RIs) – including those from Big Data. ● Developing a new advanced resilience assessment methodology based on smart RIs (“resilience indicators cube”, including the resilience matrix). The collected set of indicators is then “checked”, in order to be sure that the whole resilience assessment process is well covered, the indicators are then ordered within the resilience matrix. The matrix looks at the 4 phases of the resilience cycle (prepare, absorb, recover, adapt) and four types of indicators (physical, information, cognitive, social) ● Developing the interactive “SCI Dashboard” tool

²³ <http://www.smartresilience.eu-vri.eu/>

2.1.10 DEFENDER Project

DEFENDER²⁴ – Defending the European Energy Infrastructure – project meets the strategic challenge of protecting the CEI legacy and designing a new generation of more resilient European Energy Infrastructure. This new generation of CEI must be able to survive large scale physical and cyber-attacks and incidents, ensuring the continuity of operations and minimizing the effect on the environment, the vicinity and the energy end- users.

DEFENDER adopts a holistic approach, thinking in terms of securing the entire energy infrastructure, considering the whole aspects and not in fragmented terms, in order to enhance both physical and cyber security. The DEFENDER project pursues the following strategic objectives:

- Adaptation, integration, implementation and validation of a range of different technologies and operational projects in order to develop a new approach to safeguard European CEI from cyber, physical and social threats.
- Development of new perspectives and methodologies for the lifecycle assessment, resilience and self-healing offering “security by design”.
- Development of advanced control systems for incident mitigation and intrusion detection.
- Creation of a culture of security where trusted information exchange between trained employees and volunteers will complement cyber-physical protection, while preserving the privacy of the citizens involved.

DEFENDER combines a range of devices/technologies for situational awareness (fixed sensors like PMUs, mobile devices like drones and advanced video surveillance) (ii) intelligent processing for cyber-physical threat detection with (iii) a toolbox for incident mitigation and emergency response and (iv) Human-In-The-Loop for managing people interaction with CEI, while leveraging on blockchain technology for peer-to-peer trustworthiness.

Different layers where are included sensors and systems to detect, identify, response to, and mitigate anomalies and threats have been identified in the DEFENDER system.

The following Table 17 Table 24 shows the main tools:

Table 24: DEFENDER project's main tools

Focus: Critical Energy Infrastructure	
<p>Source Layer: The Source Layer of the DEFENDER is composed of the set of sensor devices and equipment that are able to communicate and provide information, of any kind, to the DEFENDER system.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cyber sensor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SCADA ○ Smart meter ○ Integrated security mechanisms (e.g., SIPROTEC 5) ○ Communication network elements (e.g., optical network, SDH, IP/MPLS, DCN, TCP/IP, events, logs, routing tables, topology, configurations) ○ Information System security and protection elements (e.g., firewalls, IDS/IDP and integrity management, events, logs, configurations, reports, network traffic content, protocol headers information, etc.) ○ Information System security management elements (e.g., identity management, access control management, events, logs, configurations, access control enforcement elements events, etc.)

²⁴ <https://defender-project.eu/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Information System application elements (e.g., hosts, virtualized resources, services, events, logs, installations, configurations, DNS, etc.) ○ Operation procedures elements (events, logs) ○ Business procedure elements (events, logs) ● Human sensor ● Physical sensor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Vibration, IR, strain, fiber, etc. ○ Geophone ○ Lidar sensor ○ PMZ camera ○ Thermal camera ○ RF radar
<p>Event Layer: The Event Layer of the DEFENDER is responsible to identify the threat related events. The Event Layer utilises a specialised module for detecting Cyber-security related events, as well as a second module that identifies physical-security related events. On top of those two components, there is a third one that determines Cyber-Physical events, combining the results of the Cyber Event Detection and the Physical Event Detection.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Physical Detectors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Human Intrusion ○ Person Detection and Tracking ● Cyber Detectors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Network monitoring ○ Pattern Matcher on log data ○ Access Control Event Detection ○ Optical Network Event Detection ○ SCADA Network Inventory Event Detection ○ NORM Event Detection
<p>Situation Layer: The Situation Layer compiles the overall status of the identified incident and tracks that status over time, creating an overview of the evolved security situation. The objective of the Situation Layer is to transform the events generated from the Event Layer into an assessment of the best actions to mitigate the situation, through controlled Decision Support mechanisms.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incident Mitigation DSS ● CEI Incidents DSS
<p>Service Layer: The Service Layer augments the Situation Layer information with possible counter measures, depending on the characteristics of the security situation. It constitutes a Security Control Centre and provides an Action Toolbox, which can be used to select possible counter measures and actions to heal the consequences of the Cyber or Physical security incident.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Security Control Centre ● Action Toolbox
<p>Actuator Layer: contains a set of components to mitigate the cyber-physical threats and attacks by enabling responses using drones, humans and/or virus/malware. Possible</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Drone neutralisation ● Fault Location and service recovery ● Double Virtualization ● Human In the Loop

countermeasures can include the complete destruction of the attacking drone, the signal interference, so that the drone is disconnected from its controlling point, as well as other non-destructive measures that attempt to neutralise the drone.

2.1.11 7SHIELD Project

7SHIELD²⁵ - Safety and Security Standards of Space Systems, ground Segments and Satellite data assets, via prevention, detection, response and mitigation of physical and cyber threats - aims at providing a holistic framework enable to confront complex threats by covering all the macro stages of crisis management, namely pre-crisis, crisis and post-crises phases. Specifically, the early warning mechanism estimates the level of risk before the occurrence of a cyber or physical attack. During an attack, the detection and response is effective and efficient, taking into account budgetary constraints. A mitigation plan is designed and automatically updated to offer a quick recovery after an intentional attack or a system failure. Security and resilience of private installations of space ground segments are also supported by business continuity scenarios, building on top of an innovative orchestration of novel monitoring and forecasting technologies. The 7SHIELD's technologies and tools are illustrated in Figure 16 and then listed:

Figure 16: 7SHIELD Framework

The following Table 25 shows the main tools:

Table 25: 7SHIELD project's main tools

Focus: Space Systems, ground Segments and Satellite data assets	
Prevention Technologies for Physical and Cyber Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Risk Assessment tools ● Secure authentication mechanism ● Combined threat assessment tool ● Cyber and Physical Threat Intelligence
Detection Technologies for Physical and Cyber Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data collection and edge processing ● Video surveillance technologies (Face detection and face recognition; Video-based object and activity recognition)

²⁵ <https://www.7shield.eu/project/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyber-attack detection framework • Thermal and near-infrared image processing for man-made threats detection • Innovative Laser-based technologies for the detection of ground-based and aerial threats detection • Combined Physical and Cyber Threat Detection and Early Warning
Response Technologies for Physical and Cyber Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Semantic representation and linking for reasoning and decision-making • Crisis level classification from multimodal data fusion • Tactical Decision Support System • Social awareness and warning message generation • UAV neutralisation mechanism
Mitigation Technologies for Physical and Cyber Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential impacts from C/P attacks and countermeasures knowledge base

2.1.12 InfraStress Project

The mission of InfraStress²⁶ - Improving resilience of sensitive industrial plants & infrastructures exposed to cyber-physical threats, by means of open testbed stress-testing system - is to improve the resilience and the protection capabilities of SIPS exposed to large scale, combined, cyber-physical threats and hazards, guarantee the continuity of operations, while minimizing cascading effects in the infrastructure itself, the environment, the other CIs, and the citizens in vicinity, at reasonable cost. InfraStress technological framework consists of many tools and services able to detect both cyber and physical threats and hazards; integrate C/P situational awareness and resilience; and provide decision support functionalities for the whole CIP lifecycle (preparedness, planning, prevention, detection, mitigation, response, and post-event). The systems and tools are classified as shown in Table 26:

Table 26: InfraStress project's mail tools

Focus: Sensitive industrial plants & infrastructures	
Physical and cyber threats detection and protection systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical threats and hazards detection and protection systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Laser Radar (2D LIDAR) based surveillance ○ Mini-drone detection and neutralization ○ Non-authorized People Detector ○ Building and facility diagnosis and monitoring ○ Environmental monitoring ○ Relevant event and anomaly detection from video surveillance ○ People behaviour analysis from visual data • Cyber threats and hazards detection and protection systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ BAM-Aware Intrusion Detection ○ Machine-learning based Anomaly Based Detection ○ Cyber threat detection at end-points and IIoT/SCADA

²⁶ <https://www.infrastress.eu/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Human sensors and crowdsensing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Crowd-sensing apps to get signals from the environment/vicinity ○ Detection of relevant security event and info from OSINT and social media ○ Sentiment and Emotions Detection from social networks
Integrated C/P situational awareness for SIPS CIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Situational picture for integrated cyber-physical protection of industrial sensitive sites and plants <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Relevant event handling and anomaly discovery ○ Resilience indicators dashboard and visual analytics ○ Situational picture dashboard and visual analytics ○ Identification of complex attack scenarios ○ Geospatial stream correlation engine ○ Interdependency and cascading effects impact assessment ○ Multi-dimensional descriptive analytics ● Cyber and physical threat intelligence ad prediction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ OSINT/Dark Web analysis for cyber/physical threat intelligence ○ Integration of cyber threat intelligence (TI) sources ○ Spatiotemporal forecasting of attacks and vulnerabilities
Applications and services for C/P protection of resilient industrial sensitive sites and plants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prevention and preparedness decision support services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Building Information Model ○ Vulnerability assessment ○ Security Risk assessment and analysis services ○ Simulation and impact assessment of C/P threats and hazards ○ Service to build integrated safety-security risk management plans ○ Cyber-Physical security and safety design tool to co-design and assess SIP safety/security system ○ Organizational Resilience Culture Audit ○ AR-based Training for CIP ● CIP monitoring and early warning services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Monitoring and early warning dashboards ● Response, mitigation and recovery decision support services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Services improving the protection of first responders ○ Cyber-physical policy enforcement engine ○ Rapid damage assessment ○ Crowdsourcing apps to engage citizens, volunteers, and operators ● Post-event analysis services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Prescriptive analytics for CIP improvement

2.1.13 ENSURESEC Project

ENSURESEC²⁷'s - End-to-end Security of the Digital Single Market's E-commerce and Delivery Service Ecosystem -overarching objective is to equip e-commerce infrastructures and ecosystems with through-life protection against cyber, physical and cyber-physical threats, including cascading effects, thus contributing towards the vision of a reliable and trusted European Digital Single Market.

ENSURESEC includes six main modules:

- Prevention by design: Prevention assesses and certifies that the design of the system interfaces is secure against certain classes of critical attacks and vulnerabilities.
- Detection by monitoring: Detection monitors run-time interface operations at the application level and network level for resilience against both known and unknown threats, i.e., whenever a vulnerability or arbitrary malicious activity is detected, the system continues operation in fail-safe mode
- Response and mitigation of threats and incidents: engine communicates an appropriate response to the affected users and partners and attempts to mitigate the impact
- Recovery of compromised interfaces: recovers the system's state by identifying what has gone wrong based on a dependency-directed diagnosis.
- Continuous situational awareness of threats and incidents.
- Training of SMEs and their citizen clients of e-commerce.

The ENSURESEC concept (Figure 17) is based on prevention-by-design (combined security-by-design and privacy-by-design) followed by a circular —monitoring – assessing risk – detecting incidents – mitigating risks approach to ensure through-life protection.

Figure 17: The ENSURESEC concept

The following Table 27 shows the main tools:

Table 27: ENSURESEC project's main tools

Focus: e-commerce infrastructures and ecosystems	
<p>Prevention By Design The prevention-by-design module verifies that various models that describe the e-commerce ecosystem are protected against combined cyber-physical, security and privacy threats.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping Engine • Modelling and verification • Continuity management • Ecosystem Risk and Resilience Analyzer
<p>Detection By Monitoring Though protection-by-design assures that the e-commerce ecosystem design is protected and reliable, still the actual functioning of the ecosystem may be compromised as it runs in a hostile environment. Therefore, this module enforces the security of the</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioral Monitor • Data security Monitor • Communication Monitor • Policy Monitor • Physical Asset Monitor • AI-based Incident Monitor

²⁷ <https://www.ensuresec.eu/>

ecosystem in real-time by monitoring the execution of the interfaces.	
<p>Response, Mitigation and Recovery</p> <p>Based on the detection of security incidents, this module is responsible for responding to the incident related business and services partners and their citizen clients on one hand and to initiate a corresponding mitigation strategy to eliminate or reduce the impact of the incident on the other hand. The mitigation strategy first attempts to eliminate the impact of the incident by recovering the compromised interfaces, if that is not possible, then it attempts to reduce the impact of the incident.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Response and Mitigation Engine ● Distributed Ledger ● Software Recovery Engine ● Post-event Analyser
<p>Resilient Oriented Situational Awareness</p> <p>The security of the e-commerce ecosystem involves complex threats with cascading effects and with unique cyber, cyber-physical, physical impacts. Therefore, this module goes beyond classical security situational analysis tools and aims to employ advanced machine learning and data analysis techniques to continuously perform situational analysis of suspected and current incidents and to determine their impact.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Events Correlation Engine ● Information Sharing ● (Cyber and Physical) Threat Intelligence ● Multi-level Interdependency and Cascading Effect Analyzer ● Visual Analyzer

The review of the previous EU-funded security projects revealed the multidimensionality of the CIP measures and systems. There are several ways in which security products and systems can be categorised depending on the technology itself and the context within which it is used. Technologies can also be categorised and understood as responses to particular threats, or in relation to concerns. Another type of classification is related to the phases of crisis management.

2.1.14 PANOPTIS Project

PANOPTIS²⁸ project aimed at the development of a Decision Support System for increasing the Resilience of Road Infrastructure based on combined use of terrestrial and airborne sensors and advanced modelling tools. The purpose of PANOPTIS project was to improve the resiliency (ability to adapt) of the road infrastructures and ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, landslides, and earthquakes. The project's main goal was to combine down-scale climate change scenarios (applied to road infrastructure) with structural and geotechnical simulation tools, and with actual data from sensors (terrestrial and airborne), in order to provide the operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at planning, maintenance and operation level.

Tool: Integrated Incident Management & Decision Support System for Road Operators

PANOPTIS aimed to design and develop a next generation Situation Management & Decision Support System that combines:

- Various Road Infrastructure Sensors
- Aerial Platforms
- Deep Learning based Video Analytics
- Weather Modeling Tools
- Structural modeling Tools
- Risk and Impact Assessment Tools
- Resources and Assets
- Geographical information systems

²⁸ <http://www.panoptis.eu/>

The tool main purposes are:

- Understand RI resilience to atmospheric and geotechnical hazards
- Manage planned and unplanned events / incidents with Decision Support
- Acquire Early Warning and Situational Awareness capabilities
- Respond via Standard Operating Procedures

The main benefits are:

- Software-as-a-Service or on Premise
- Integration of unique and diverse tools and services for RI Situational Awareness & Decision Support
 - ✓ Prediction Services
 - ✓ Impact Assessment Services
 - ✓ Warning & Alerts
 - ✓ Specialized Video Analytics
 - ✓ What if / What is
- Standard Operating Procedures fully customizable by RI Operators
- Data on the Move

2.1.15 STAR-TRANS Project

The objective of the STAR-TRANS²⁹ project was to produce a Security Risk Assessment Framework for European interconnected and interdependent transportation networks. The proposed Security Risk Assessment Framework includes:

1. A modelling formalism capable of representing:
 - possible risk incidents on European transportation networks.
 - structure and assets of European transportation networks.
 - dependency types between assets of transportation networks.
2. A software tool capable of:
 - managing European interconnected and interdependent transportation networks' structure and assets as well as dependencies between the involved assets.
 - assessing and reporting the impact that a specific risk incident on assets of a European transportation network may have on the assets of interconnected and interdependent transportation networks.

Impact Assessment Tool (IAT)

IAT provides the technology to link together any relevant assets of interconnected and interdependent transport networks, such that risk managers, policy makers and others can, subsequently, be provided with the impact a risk incident has on assets of other interconnected and interdependent transport networks.

The Impact Assessment Tool (IAT) can be conceptually split in three different and discrete tools which are described in more detail in the following sections:

1. **The Network Modelling Tool (NM)** that handles the representation of the transportation network, describing its assets and their interdependencies. The Network Modelling Tool builds upon asset and network data already available in IAT through the IA Tool to formulate the integral part of the STAR-TRANS framework, the network-of-networks. The tool allows to define networks-of-networks as an entity at the top level of the network hierarchy. The tool implements the following types of asset interdependencies: Physical, Systems, Geographic and Logical. The tool defines the following network hierarchy:
 - The “network-of-networks”
 - Transportation networks that belong to the “network-of-networks”
 - Assets that belong to a predefined network of the “network-of-networks”

Users entitled with the “Asset Manager” role use predefined networks and their assets to further define networks-of-networks as an entity at the top level of the network hierarchy. The tool is “locale-aware”,

²⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/225594/reporting>

meaning that user and network data are organized on a geographical area basis, which allows the tool to limit the access of Asset Managers from a particular geographical area to the networks belonging to this area only.

The tool implements the following types of asset interdependencies: Physical, Systems, Geographic and Logical.

Thus, the Asset Manager provides fundamental information about the structure of each network-of-networks that is a prerequisite for the STML Engine Core (STEC) in order to evaluate impact propagation and assess overall risk. In the context of the NM tool a publication workflow is employed at the network-of-networks level to dissociate the network-of-networks that have been thoroughly processed and are available for public use within IAT from those that are still in draft mode and are only accessible by the user that created them.

NM relies on communication with STML Engine Core (STEC), the component of the STAR-TRANS framework that performs all modeling functions, maintains the state of the networks and evaluates risk. The NM – STEC communication for network modeling are implemented with web services and ensure an integrated experience to the end user. STML Engine Core is built using the principles of Software as a Service (SaaS) and provides a standardized, well documented and thoroughly tested back-end interface to the STAR-TRANS front-end tool or any other impact assessment software. With this approach, the GUI part of any impact assessment tool is fully decoupled from the actual back-end, where the core risk evaluation process takes place.

An integrated access control mechanism ensures that a network-of-networks is edited only by the user that defined it, while all other Asset Managers have the right to view or clone it to a new network-of-networks.

Main benefits obtained:

- Advanced graphical representation of a network-of-networks using an intuitive Google Maps interface
 - Create/Read/Update/Delete operations on the asset interdependencies
 - Create/Read/Update/Delete operations on the network-of-networks level
2. **The Risk Modelling Tool (RM)** that represents threat scenarios as networks of primary and propagated incidents and consequences on assets. Essentially, RM is a tool for Security Managers to model long- and short-term risk using Threat Scenarios that are sets of the following primary elements:
- Incident – Asset pairs that are combined to represent adverse events occurring in a particular timeframe
 - Likelihood of occurrence for each Incident – Asset pair within the Threat Scenario
 - Consequences of each Incident – Asset pair within the Threat Scenario
 - Impact Propagation on interdependent assets
- The Incident – Asset pairs of a Threat Scenario are not handled as a sequence of events on a timeline, rather as an aggregation of events that should be quantitatively analyzed typically drawing upon past experience in order to proactively manage risk.
- In RM implementation the approach of a setup wizard (Threat Scenario Setup Wizard) is employed. The Security Manager is presented with a sequence of frames that lead him through a series of well-defined steps. This simplified the lengthy and complex process of fully configuring a Threat Scenario.
3. **The Risk Analysis Tool (RA)** that acts as a decision tool to ensure that realistic targets and commitments are established. The Risk Analysis Tool comprises the following modules:
- Response Procedure Module (ReP): Each Response Procedure is associated with an Incident-Asset pair and is also linked to a network-of-networks. The Risk Analyst gains an overview of this related network-of-networks on a map, where the outer cordon of the incident scene should be interactively defined. Additionally, the Risk Analyst defines the emergency and evacuation vehicles origin and destination respectively as well as purpose. Along, with number of lane closures and incident duration, ReP communicates this information to VISTA through web service calls which calculates routing of emergency vehicles.
 - Risk Output Evaluation Module (Rout-eval): Having estimated the impact and likelihood of each risk, the Risk Output Evaluation Module (Rout-eval) assess the overall risk contained within a network, network of networks or area of effect with respect to a specific Threat Scenario. Rout-eval captures all parameters related to a Threat Scenario to equip Risk Analysts with a tool that offers them the following information:
 - Graphical representation of the position of a selected Incident – Asset pair on a map

- Indication of the overall risk involved with this Incident – Asset pair
- List of propagated incidents
- Overview of the corresponding Response Procedure
- The overall risk of the asset involved in the pair, its corresponding network and network-of-networks.

The output of Risk Analysis is a valuable decision assistance tool both to ensure that realistic targets and commitments are established, but also to make choices among alternative courses of action that offer different levels of risk and costs, savings or other consequences. Options available to the parties controlling the transportation network or network of networks can be integrated into the analysis to evaluate their overall impact on a particular course of action.

4. **The IAT Administration Tool (IA)** that manages the import of historical data, impact propagation matrix, threat – consequences matrix and other important data for the risk evaluation process, as well as user profiles, roles and authorization. The IAT main requirement is the development of an intuitive interface for security experts to be able to model asset dependencies, threats and incidents, consequences, incidents' history database and the STAR-TRANS impact propagation process, to uniquely address risk assessment in the network-of-networks through risk scenarios evaluation. The IAT Administrators are equipped with intuitive graphical user interfaces to perform the following set of tasks:

- User Management
- Configure generic risk, likelihood and propagation parameters
- Import the structure of all the IAT networks represented in XML format
- Import historical data about the frequency of an incident occurrence to be used as key element for likelihood estimation

The benefits of the system are that risk managers can view a graphical representation the impact of an incident response has on the interconnected and interdependent transport networks as well as determine alternative flows for the affected elements of transportation networks.

2.1.16 SAFECARE Project

The aim of the SAFECARE³⁰ is to provide solutions that will improve physical and cyber security in a seamless and cost-effective way. It promotes new technologies and novel approaches to enhance threat prevention, threat detection, incident response and mitigation of impacts. The project will also participate in increasing the compliance between security tools and European regulations about ethics and privacy for health services. The end goal of the SAFECARE project is to protect healthcare infrastructures, and eventually the safety of the patient, by fostering the creation of solutions for the improvement of cyber and physical security in the current healthcare context. SAFECARE global solution has been designed for the improvement of cyber and physical security in the healthcare context.

The SAFECARE global architecture can be broken down into 3 parts:

- Physical security solutions
- Cyber security solutions
- Integrated cyber-physical security solutions.

The physical security solutions and the cyber security solutions consist of smart modules and efficient integrated technologies to respectively improve physical security and cyber security. More specifically, physical security solutions embed integrated intelligent video monitoring and interconnect building monitoring systems as well as management systems. Meanwhile, cyber security solutions correspond to cyber monitoring systems as well as threat detection systems related to information technology (IT), building management system (BMS) and e-health systems. Both physical security solutions and cyber security solutions are interconnected thanks to the integrated cyber-physical security solutions. The integrated cyber-physical security solutions consist of intelligent modules whose role is to integrate different data sources and better take into account the combination of physical and cyber security threats [55].

The main project's tools are shown in Table 28:

³⁰ <https://www.safecare-project.eu/>

Table 28: SAFECARE project's main tools

Focus: healthcare context	
Physical security solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The suspicious behaviour detection system (SBDS) • The intrusion and fire detection system (IFDS) • The data collection system (DCS) • The mobile alerting system (MAS) • The building threat monitoring system (BTMS)
Cyber security solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The IT threat detection system (ITTDS) • The BMS threat detection system (BTDS) • The advanced file analysis system (AFAS) • The e-health devices security analytics (EDSA) • The cyber threat monitoring system (CTMS)
Integrated cyber-physical security solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The data exchange layer (DXL) • The central database (CDB) • The impact propagation and decision support model (IPDSM) • The threat response and alert system (TRAS) • The hospital availability management system (HAMS) • The e-health security risk management model

2.1.17 SATIE Project

SATIE's³¹ (Security of Air Transport Infrastructure of Europe) ambition is to design, develop, integrate and demonstrate a set of different Innovation Elements (IEs) in order to improve the state of the art in airport security by solving the pre-identified conceptual, technical, economical, and societal limitations. SATIE adopts a holistic approach about threat prevention, detection, response and mitigation in the airports, while guaranteeing the protection of critical systems, sensitive data and passengers. Critical assets are usually protected against individual physical or cyber threats, but not against complex scenarios combining both categories of threats. In order to handle it, SATIE develops an interoperable toolkit which improves cyber-physical correlations, forensics investigations and dynamic impact assessment at airports.

The type of the classification adopted in the project to classify the systems and technologies provided was organized around the phases of the crisis management (threat prevention, detection, response and mitigation).

More specifically, in the context of the project several Security Solutions are deployed in critical areas in order to detect and prevent potential threats in airport environments. A **Correlation Engine** gathers information coming from detectors and airport systems and triggers aggregated alerts in real time.

Two **Impact Propagation Tools** relying on an interdependency model between IT assets, airport operations, and business processes, provide an impact assessment and decision support to the **Security Operation Centre (SOC)** and the **Airport Operation Centre (AOC)**.

An **Investigation Tool** unifies the physical and cyber security investigation and performs a deep analysis of activities and threats over a long time-frame to identify alerts stemming from the same attack.

For the operator in the SOC, an **Incident Management Portal (IMP)** displays aggregated alerts and provides contextual information about security events, targeted assets, and exploitable vulnerabilities.

For those in the AOC, a **Crisis Alerting System (CAS)** improves collaboration and coordination with the SOC, first responders, and other airport stakeholders for a faster security and safety response [56].

The main project's tools are shown in Table 29:

Table 29: SATIE project's main tools

Focus: Security of Air Transport Infrastructure of Europe

³¹ <https://satie-h2020.eu/>

<p>Correlation Engine (Prevention, Detection)</p>	<p>The Correlation Engine is the central system of the SATIE Toolkit whose objective it is to aggregate and correlate information from the entire SATIE Toolkit. The Correlation Engine triggers alerts to the Incident Management Portal based on a set of user-defined correlation rules.</p> <p>The Correlation Engine aggregates information from the entire SATIE Toolkit (cyber and physical events). Alerts raised by the Correlation Engine are forwarded to the IMP and presented to the SOC operator in one of four severity levels (high, medium, low, info).</p> <p>The Correlation Engine as the core system of the SATIE Toolkit aggregates data from cyber and physical events from other Supporting Systems and the Threat Prevention and Detection Systems to correlate them based on a set of specified rules. Information on detected threats is forwarded to the Incident Management Portal. The information is presented in a consolidated way to the SOC operators.</p>
<p>Impact Propagation Tools (Response, Impact mitigation)</p>	<p>Within the SATIE toolkit, two Impact Propagation Tools visualize the impact of attacks on the cyber and physical assets, passengers, staff, and business processes to provide decision support to the SOC and AOC operators and assist in impact mitigation. These are the Impact Propagation Simulation and the Business Impact Assessment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Impact Propagation Simulation focusses on how an attack’s impact propagates through the airport’s assets and influences passengers’ behaviour by employing the combination of two propagation models: a Network Model and an Agent-based Model (ABM). - The Network Model is a topological representation of the cyber and physical assets – including airport staff and passengers – as nodes (shown as numbered circles) and their interconnections, e.g. information flows or wiring, as edges (shown as lines connecting the circles). - The Agent-based Model is employed to simulate the physical movement of passengers at the airport. The central infrastructures – doors, check-in areas, security controls, Flight Information Display System monitors, and gates – are approximated and visually modelled • The Business Impact Assessment as second Impact Propagation Tool analyses how business-critical processes and goals are affected by an attack. The impact assessment is performed to identify assets in the airport’s infrastructure affected by threat propagation and determine the critical services compromised. The assessment further analyses the impacts the affected services may cause on the airport’s business-critical processes. <p>The main purpose of the Impact Propagation Simulation is to provide information on how an attack’s impact propagates through the airport’s assets and influences passengers’ behaviour, while the Business Impact Assessment as second Impact Propagation Tool analyses how business-critical processes and goals are affected by an attack.</p> <p>The SOC and AOC operators are employed with both, a holistic overview of impacted assets and details of how airport processes are affected and the impacts of the affected services on the airport’s business-critical processes.</p>
<p>Investigation Tools (Response, Impact mitigation)</p>	<p>The Investigation Tool developed (SMS-I), represents SATIE’s innovation in what concerns the need to deal with the analysis of data from heterogeneous systems, over different time frames, and to provide insights about evidence of the causes of an attack. SMS-I is a tool that receives events and alerts from the Correlation Engine and incidents marked by the SOC operator within the Incident Management Portal.</p>

	<p>The Investigation Tool (SMS-I) unifies the physical and cybersecurity investigation. It performs a deep analysis of activities and threats over a long timeframe to identify, in real-time, alerts stemming from the same attack. SMS-I also supports the fast recovery in case of an incident by analysing past mitigation strategies using Machine Learning (ML) techniques.</p> <p>Security investigation aims to explore the cause of an attack and how much it threatened the security of the targeted property. In case the security of a system is compromised, investigating over the information collected during the monitoring phase can bring important insights, both to improve detection and prevention, and to support mitigation and remediation strategies.</p>
<p>Incident Management Portal (Response, Impact mitigation)</p>	<p>The Incident Management Portal is the main system interacted with by the SOC operator. Through two software solutions, CymID and Cymerius, it offers a central place to access all Supporting Systems and Threat Prevention and Detection Systems that provide a Graphical User Interface (GUI). Furthermore, all alerts raised by the SATIE Tools are aggregated here and can be managed, analysed, and shared with the Crisis Alerting System. The design of the Incident Management Portal is suitable to be used in all environments and provides a global and coherent approach to the monitoring of information systems' security. It continuously provides the key indicators on the security of the system together with relevant information, so that the severity and consequences of a complex attack or major alert are understood by all SOC operators, independent of their level and scope of duties. The CymID software is a Single Sign-On (SSO) solution enabling the SOC operator to access a multitude of tools without them having to sign in for each separately.</p> <p><i>The Incident Management Portal</i> displays aggregated alerts and provides contextual information about security events, targeted assets, and exploitable vulnerabilities to the SOC operators.</p> <p>The design of the Incident Management Portal is suitable to be used in all environments and provides a global and coherent approach to the monitoring of information systems' security. It continuously provides the key indicators on the security of the system together with relevant information, so that the severity and consequences of a complex attack or major alert are understood by all SOC operators, independent of their level and scope of duties.</p>
<p>Crisis Alerting System (CAS) (Response, Impact mitigation)</p>	<p>The Crisis Alerting System is the main tool used by the AOC operators, improving the communication between SOC and AOC operators, and the decision-making and incident management process. Additionally, CAS enables communication among the AOC operators and the first responders, airport stakeholders, and citizens that are close to the airport or are using the airport facilities and could therefore be affected by an incident.</p> <p>AOC operators are able to monitor the airport by checking the information coming from its various security and safety systems (e.g. CCTV cameras). This information is depicted in the CAS's Graphical User Interface and enhanced with information produced by the SOC and the Impact Propagation Simulation. In that way, AOC operators are able to have a better view of the situation at the airport, consequently improving their response activities, like informing affected passengers and contacting first responders. Additionally, standard operating procedures in the form of action lists are depicted to the operators, guiding their actions. Moreover, the Crisis Alerting System enables communication between the AOC operators and the third-party agencies that are responsible to respond to an emergency</p>

situation. In case of an emergency, AOC operators are able to communicate with safety agencies, such as the Fire Service, the Emergency Medical Service, etc., sharing operation information useful to the situation. This communication between the AOC operators and involved agencies improves the situation awareness, collaboration, and the coordination of the response activities. In cases where the notification of citizens is required, AOC operators (through CAS) are able to alert them. The smart notification service takes into account the characteristics of a situation (such as the location, type, criticality, etc.) in order to route the notification only to citizens that are close to or affected by the situation.

The main benefits of the System are as follows:

The **generation of the operational picture** by combining information from security and safety systems of the airport with information provided by the SOC and the Impact Propagation Simulation.

Smart notification and alerting service enables the information sharing among involved actors at every level of coordination during a crisis by enabling collaborative response and at the same time supporting multichannel alerting of passengers and of possibly affected population, with variable content according to their location.

2.1.18 CIPROTECTION Project

CIPROTECTION³² project "Targeted Actions for enhancing the protection of National Characterized European Critical Infrastructure – NCECI", includes a series of actions and deliverables that are being developed in order to provide the background for a commonly acceptable level of safety and protection for the NCECI. To this end, it is critical to ensure the systematic cooperation of the bodies that are responsible for the safety and protection of citizens with the operators and in particular the Security Managers of the Infrastructures. Its main goal is to define a framework of synergies between those involved in security, protection and the sound operation of infrastructures that will contribute to the strengthening of the resilience of society, for the smooth operation of which, critical infrastructure constitute a key pillar.

KE.ME.A. within its current Action and related activities in the field of Critical Infrastructure Protection is developing a pilot Coordination Center in its premises, following the supply of equipment and cut-edge GIS software. The main objective of the Center is the possibility of exchanging information among the crisis management agencies and first responders and the operators and managers of Critical Infrastructures in security-related topics. The national platform for national CIs and the under-development information system aims at the systematic information of the Infrastructure operators for their level of risk after analysis of natural and technological risks and anthropogenic threats. In addition, infrastructure operators are requested to provide pilot reporting of emergency safety and security incidents exceeding the limits of their Infrastructure, through a secure online application, in order to inform the competent authorities and to contribute to the register of security incidents. The scientific elaboration of the latter, in collaboration with the Infrastructure and the operational bodies, is done for reasons of improvement of the infrastructure protection plan at national level. The Center and its operations are developed according to the standards of European CIWIN and ERNCIP.

Tool: Coordination Center (CC) for Critical Infrastructure Protection

The CC manages any risk / threat that may have an impact on the operation of infrastructure and has a spatial dimension and can be defined with geographical coordinates. The way hazards / threats information is managed by the CC is the same, regardless of the type of risk (all hazards approach).

The purposes of the CC are:

- Strengthening public-private sector partnership and communication on security issues
- Continuous exchange of views and good practices for improving the level of infrastructure security

³² <http://www.ciprotection.gr/index.php/en/>

- Ability to exchange information and information among a) the National Authorities b) the Emergency Response Agencies involved; and c) the operators / managers of the Critical Infrastructures
- Enhancing public-private cooperation and communication on security issues
- Continuous exchange of views and good practices to improve the level of infrastructures security
- Ability to exchange information among a) national authorities b) emergency responders involved in CI protection c) CI operators.
- The CC also has pilot function for research and informative purposes to the CIs operators and state Institutions

The main benefits:

- Establishment and systematization of cooperation between CI operators and emergency responders
- Sensibilization of CI operators to security and risk management issues
- Improvement of the exchange and flow of information on the identification and management of risks and threats
- Collection of typological vulnerability estimates
- Support of CI operators for the improvement of CI security with hazard identification of the CI surrounding area and CI risk assessment
- Research on real incidents and their management for the development of strategies based on actual data
- Enhancement of operational capabilities of CIs
- Protection of citizen life quality with uninterrupted operation of CIs

2.1.19 INFRARISK Project

INFRARISK³³ - Novel Indicators for identifying critical INFRAstructure at RISK from natural hazards (FP7-ENV-2013-two-stage). The core objective of INFRARISK project is to develop a stress test framework to tackle the coupled impacts of natural hazards on interdependent infrastructure networks through:

- Identifying rare low-frequency natural hazard events, which have the potential to have extreme impacts on critical infrastructure.
- Developing a stress test structure for specific natural hazards on CI networks and a framework for linear infrastructure systems with wider extents and many nodal points (roads, highways and railroads), though it is anticipated the outputs can be applied across a variety of networks (e.g telecom, energy).
- An integrated approach to hazard assessment considering the interdependencies of infrastructure networks, the correlated nature of natural hazards, cascading hazards and cascading effects, and spatial and temporal vulnerability.
- Facilitate implementation through the development of GIS based and web-based stress test algorithms for complex infrastructure networks.
- Testing the framework developed through simulation of complex, case studies.
- Exploitation strategies aimed at disseminating the 'knowledge' and not just the results (e.g training courses to industry, academic and media parties).

As INFRARISK developed stress test methodologies, the protection measures were classified according to the stress level to which they are applied.

The main developed tools in the context of the project are the following:

- Reliable stress test procedures expanded and adapted to land-based CI leading to resilient infrastructure networks to rare and low probability extreme events.
- Decision making approaches for better protection of existing infrastructure while achieving more robust strategies for the development of new ones.

³³ <https://www.infrarisk-fp7.eu/>

- Integrated risk mitigation scenarios and strategies using local, national and pan-European infrastructure risk analysis methodologies taking into consideration multiple hazards and risks with cascading impact assessments.
- Robust modelling of spatio-temporal processes with propagated dynamic uncertainties in multiple risk complexity scenarios of Known Unknowns and Unknown Unknowns.
- Operational framework with cascading hazards, impacts and dependent geospatial vulnerabilities and practical software tools and guidelines to provide greater support to the next generation of European infrastructure managers.
- Collaborative integrated platform where risk management professionals' access and share data, information and risk scenarios results efficiently and intuitively.

Stress Test Methodology and Decision Support Tool

INFRARISK Developed a stress test structure that can consider the impact of specific natural hazards on critical infrastructure networks. This work adapted nuclear stress test methodologies, similar to those developed in Japan post Fukushima, to develop a Decision Support Tool that can consider linear infrastructure systems that have wider extents and many nodal points. In general, this project focused on such nodal “land-links” such as roads, highways and railroads, though the outputs can be applied to a variety of networks, such as electricity, telecoms, tunnels, and pipelines etc.

The Stress Test methodology was developed to establish the resilience of critical European infrastructures to rare low frequency extreme events and to aid decision making in the long term regarding robust infrastructure development and protection of existing infrastructure.

A Considerable amount of stress testing has been accrued within the mechanical engineering industry. Accelerated Life Testing (ALT) is one such method whereby a component is tested by subjecting it to conditions more than its normal service parameters in an effort to uncover faults and potential modes of failure in a short amount of time. ALT is typically applied to many kinds of structures, such as airplane wings, mobile telephones etc. Application of the methodology to CI with environmental variables such as temperature, water level, precipitation, and wind speed was the novel aspect of the INFRARISK approach. This was achieved through the application of The Morlet continuous wavelet transforms to mathematical stress testing. This means that CI owners for the first time could demonstrate the level of stress their infrastructure could sustain, based on realistic observations.

2.1.20 RAIN Project

RAIN³⁴ - Risk Analysis of Infrastructure Networks in response to extreme weather (FP7-SEC-2013-1) vision is to provide an operational analysis framework that identifies critical infrastructure components impacted by extreme weather events and minimise the impact of these events on the EU infrastructure network. The project has a core focus on land-based infrastructure with a much wider consideration of the ancillary infrastructure network in order to identify cascading and inter-related infrastructure issues. A core component of the research will consider the implications of climate change and the subsequent impacts that this may have on an already ageing and vulnerable infrastructure system. The impact of these disruptions on both the key components and the wider pan-European network will be assessed using economic and social markers that will identify and rank a series of “worst case” scenarios. Technical and Logistic solutions will be developed to minimise the impact of these extreme events, which will include novel early warning systems, decision support tools and engineering solutions to ensure rapid reinstatement of the network. These tools will be implemented within a fresh Europe-wide operational and response strategy that will build on previous European infrastructure models. The robustness of the existing transport and energy networks to deal with changing weather conditions will be analysed in detail. The ability of this response plan to transcend borders will be guaranteed by the multi-disciplinary consortium. The project grouping will have expertise in climatology, operational analysis, transportation economics, risk analysis and mitigation, emergency planning, transportation engineering as well as engineering design and assessment. The outputs from the project will result in enhanced safety and reliability of critical infrastructure networks in the case of major weather induced disruptions and will address European policy in the areas of safety and security, inter-modality and emergency response planning.

³⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/608166>

The categories of CIP in RAIN can be classed as Mitigation, Adaptation and Coping, but this chosen classification is not in itself the 'substance' but rather the 'form' of the appropriate responses. In general, i) Coping is very short-term, and it is clear that 'coping' is a simpler response (assuming it is feasible) than mitigation or adaptation actions, and ii) Mitigation or adaptation responses might both refer to capital, operation, or other changes (such as design changes). Additional classifications were broken down into the following:

- a) preventive (protection), which are focused on minimization of security risks connected to the threat of intrusion into, or destruction of individual facilities of the element,
- b) managerial-organizational work, whose substance lies in planning and organizing of methodical and practical training of persons that provide protection of CTI elements and in creation of effective procedure for hazards of intrusion into, or destruction of individual CTI element facilities, focusing on elimination or lowering of presumed consequences – casualties, damage to health, property or other socially adverse impacts.

The ultimate objective of the RAIN project is to enhance infrastructure robustness through developing more appropriate reactive strategies. The RAIN project was oriented on critical infrastructure protection through development of new processes and application of known processes, tools and methods that provide consistent, integrated and objective directions for risk management application in the process of critical infrastructure elements protection in transportation, energy and telecommunications sectors.

In the context of the project, a **Systematic Risk Management Framework** has been developed.

The RAIN vision is to develop a systematic risk management framework that explicitly considers the impacts of extreme weather events on critical infrastructure and develops a series of mitigation tools to enhance the security of the pan-European infrastructure network.

With this main, the activities that has been done are the following:

- quantify the complex interactions between weather events and land-based infrastructure systems (i.e. transport, telecoms, energy etc.)
- develop an operational analysis framework that considers the impact of individual hazards and the coupled interdependencies of critical infrastructure through robust risk and uncertainty modelling interactions between weather events and land-based transportation systems.
- Considering cascading hazards, cascading effects and time dependent vulnerability.
- Develop Technical and Logistic solutions to minimize the impact of these extreme events, include novel early warning systems, decision support tools and engineering solutions to ensure rapid reinstatement of the infrastructure network.

2.1.21 RESILENS Project

RESILENS³⁵ – Realising European Resilience for Critical Infrastructure (H2020-EU.3.7 H2020-EU.3.7) has an ambitious but achievable and practically applied research agenda that will result in significant advancements in the resilience of CI. The project has a wide range of technical objectives, as well as striving to deliver objectives for positive advancements in societal, economic, environmental and organisational resilience.

In an era that has seen critical infrastructure suffer from a multitude of high impact natural and manmade disasters there is a greater need than ever before to assess to the resilience of modern societies to withstand and recover from adverse events. The RESILENS project aims to further significant advancements in the resilience of critical infrastructure through practically applied research.

From a technical perspective, the project objectives are as follows:

- The operationalisation of crisis and disaster resilience concepts for Critical Infrastructure (CI). This will involve the applied integration of risk management approaches and resilience management by providing

³⁵ <http://resilens.eu/>

a solution that will support the more efficient uptake of risk assessments by Member States and Associated Countries in combination with resilience management approaches.

- The strengthening of Critical Infrastructure (CI) for water, energy, transport, housing/shelter, food, communications, finance and health which provide essential services and underpin socio-economic activity.
- More effective and coherent crises and disaster resilience management, including improved trainings for rescuers and population engagement.
- The fusion of concepts from multiple traditions including, engineering infrastructure, psychology, ecosystem stability, the behavioural sciences and disaster risk reduction to remove ambiguities and ensure coherent and agreed approaches across stakeholder disciplines.
- Build on and advance the findings of the European Programme for Critical Infrastructure Protection (EPCIP), the EU demonstration project, DRIVER (DRiving InnoVation in crisis management for European Resilience), and relevant Seventh Framework Programme.

These overarching objectives will guide the RESILENS project, which will result in the development of a RESILENS Decision Support Platform (RES-DSP) that encompasses as its major component a European Resilience Management Guideline (ERMG) which will be based on the principles of risk management and vulnerability reduction, thereby bridging the link between these two technically and conceptually interdependent processes. Resilience management tools including a Resilience Management Matrix and Audit Toolkit and substitution methods, and an E-Learning Hub will form part of the ERMG and will also be available as stand-alone applications on the RES-DSP.

Specifically, the developed tools have been classified based on Principles of Resilience, i.e., measures implemented previous to, during and after the hazardous event.

Within the context of RESILENS, an important theme was the transformation from CIP to one of **CIR (CI Resilience)**, from single infrastructures to multi-sector and from individual risk to an all-hazards approach.

Despite the more widespread use of resilience as a term, CI stakeholders indicated that risk and resilience practices had more in common with the CIP approach, often being siloed, hierarchical and utilising 'command and control' structures, rather than being part of a more widespread, everyday practice. The Resilens approach began to breach this shortcoming.

2.1.22 SPEAR Project

SPEAR³⁶ (DS-07-2017 - Cybersecurity PPP: Addressing Advanced Cyber Security Threats and Threat Actors) (Secure and PrivatE smArt gRid) project is a research program, funded by the Horizon 2020 framework programme of the European Union and it aims at developing an integrated platform of methods, processes, and tools for:

- timely detecting evolved security attacks using big data analytics, advanced visual-aided anomaly detection tools, and smart node trust management schemes
- developing an advanced forensic readiness framework for collecting attack traces and preparing the necessary legal evidence in court, while preserving user private information
- implementing an anonymous smart grid channel for mitigating the lack of trust in exchanging sensitive information about cyberattack incidents
- performing risk analysis and awareness through cyber hygiene frameworks, while empowering EU-wide consensus, by collaborating with European and global security organizations, standardization bodies, industrial groups and smart grid operators
- exploiting the research outcomes to more critical infrastructure domains, while creating competitive business models for utilizing the implemented security tools in smart grid operators and actors across Europe.

In the context of the project, the protection is mainly done by detection in non-harmful devices (the honeypots in the net). Deception technologies such as honeypots are being used as part of the cyber defence strategy of an organization in order to protect critical assets in the system. The greatest impact of the deception mechanisms is at detection area. the SPEAR Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI)honeypots

³⁶ <https://www.spear2020.eu/>

and the SPEAR Honeypot Manager. The honeypots, in general, play the role of deception technology within an overall cyber defence strategy of an organization, and specifically the SPEAR AMI honeypots emulate smart grid devices' behaviour, therefore they can act as a decoy to lure attackers while distracting them away from smart grid devices of real value. On the other hand, the Honeypot Manager provides two main functionalities: (i) acts as a decision support system that offers the optimal configuration of AMI honeypots given a smart grid infrastructure using game theory models; and (ii) supports the smart grid end user automating and deploying different type of AMI honeypots:

- **RTU honeypots** emulate real RTU devices located in smart grid substations that control devices by transmitting telemetry data to a distributed control system or SCADA, or by receiving actions from the distributed control system or SCADA. As such, the RTUs use multiple industrial communication protocols at operation phase. These honeypots allow the detection in advance of attacks on RTUs.
- **NeuralPot** is a Conpot-based honeypot that leverages a Deep Neural Network (DNN) and particularly a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) [35] in order to emulate efficiently the Modbus/TCP network traffic and particularly the Modbus/TCP response packets generated by real field devices, such as a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), a Remote Terminal Unit (RTU), smart meters, etc. This honeypot is useful to emulate any type of device, producing or consuming MODBUS data (PLC, RTU, etc).
- **SPEAR SIEM** allows the detection of anomalies and cyberattacks on Smart Grids, from heterogeneous data format and collecting info from real devices as well as honeypots. This SIEM is tuned for Smart Grid use cases and tested for Advanced metering infrastructure (AMI), Smart Grids.

2.1.23 SDN-MICROSENSE

In SDN-MICROSENSE³⁷, the SDN-microSENSE **Risk Assessment Framework(S-RAF)** has been developed. S-RAF differentiates from other risk assessment tools and acts as a complementary tool for the security of EPES infrastructure. More specifically, the following four are the main key points of differentiation between the adoption of S-RAF methodology and other risk assessment solutions: a) the cumulative risk assessment, b) the calculation methodology, c) the EPES-focused risk assessment and d) the deep insights on the security of EPES. S-RAF assesses the level of risk in all the involved EPES devices and systems by analysing a) current smart & IoT devices, b) legacy SCADA & ICS devices, c) smart meters d) other software/hardware devices connected to EPES network and e) all the energy-related personnel and stakeholders (energy operators, consumers, prosumers, energy utilities, energy generators, energy actors & agents and energy retailers). S-RAF is a risk analysis framework oriented for Electrical Power and Energy Systems (EPES). This framework is based on OLISTIC (<https://www.olistic.io>) and acts as input for the SDN self-healing tool, to protect EPES devices.

Within the S-RAF framework, different components interact:

- **SDN-SELF**: The Self-Healing component of SDN is comprised of several subcomponents to react, modify or recover elements. This is an abstraction layer to cover different incidents in a single-entry point (e.g.: attacks notified from S-RAF or casual energy failures to invoke restoration). It acts as a Central collector of anomalies or attacks to EPES.
- **EDAE**: Subcomponent of the SDN-SELF handling network topologies in the whole system, based on incidents and mitigation definitions given by the tool S-RAF. Protecting EPES assets from network attacks. The target components are reconfigured in different, clean, secure networks and then provided the new network settings to other secure elements to interact with.

2.1.24 SPARTA Project

SPARTA³⁸ project created a long-lasting community capable of collaboration to define, develop, share, and evolve solutions that will help practitioners prevent cybercrime and enhance cybersecurity. SPARTA has reimagined the way cybersecurity research, innovation, and training are performed in Europe across domains and expertise, from foundations to applications, in academia and industry.

³⁷ <https://www.sdnmicrosense.eu/>

³⁸ <https://www.sparta.eu/>

- The **T-SHARK Program** in SPARTA means to establish a Full- Spectrum Cybersecurity Threat Intelligence Framework by developing comprehensive solutions based on novel technology developments and cross-disciplinary breakthroughs. T-Shark will develop and validate methodological, organizational and technological solutions extending cybersecurity towards comprehensive organization of security functions, enabling threat prediction and full-spectrum cybersecurity awareness, providing high situational awareness, informing decision and policy makers on broad or long-term issues and/or providing a timely warning of threats. It will expand the reach of threat understanding, from current investigative-level definition, up to strategic considerations on current, future and down to real-time events handling and prevention. It will allow in near future to establish EU cybersecurity capability to predict complex cyber threats and prevent them before damage appeared. T-SHARK UE program aiming at cybersecurity awareness has selected the OS MISP project for shared, heterogeneous threat intelligence models into a common model. The MISP project contains visualization tools and interfaces to subscribe to real time events. MISP is not part of SPARTA-TSHARK, it is the tool chosen by T-SHARK. It is an Open-source software solution for collecting, storing, distributing, and sharing cyber security indicators and threats about cyber security incidents analysis and malware analysis. A platform to share different attacks models and definitions into a common-entry point.
- The **SAFAIR Program**'s role in SPARTA lies in conducting a thorough analysis of the threats and risks for AI. This is followed by providing mechanisms and tools to counter the deteriorating effects of recognized dangers in a variety of critical AI applications, making them safe and secure from the possibility of being compromised. By the same token, the program's impact on explainability will help AI users gain valuable insight into how the algorithms perform their tasks, which is particularly useful in domains where AI has already exceeded human performance. Finally, the work on fairness provides mechanisms and tools to ensure that the models created with AI methods do not rely on a skewed or prejudiced view of the situation they deal with. The evaluation of machine learning models' robustness in adversarial settings is not a trivial task. If the model is robust to a particular kind of attack, it is not a sufficient measure of its robustness. In order to have confidence in the predictions made by the model, one needs to check its robustness against a variety of attack techniques. The purpose is to evaluate and detect flaws in IA techniques for security when adversarial attacks are performed instead of conventional ones. Countermeasures for protection depending on the IA attack are also presented. Protection against attacks on the IA assessing the security. These kinds of attacks against the IA (ML, DL, etc.) security algorithms evaluating the assets health (instead of attacking the assets directly) are not covered in the existing protection systems. CI protection systems are steadily adding IA techniques for early detection, so protection against these new attack vectors is also necessary.
- The **CAPE Program** in SPARTA addresses assessment of cybersecurity properties for software, with a focus on two specific areas, cyber-physical systems and complex systems of systems. For cyber-physical systems, our objective is to propose a method to jointly specify security and safety properties, what we call security-safety codesign. The main challenge is the complexity of the co-design to address all the certification schemes. For complex systems of systems, our objective is to take into account the DevOps paradigm, where services are deployed at the same time as they are being developed, and where they are leveraging a lot of external libraries. The challenge here is to extend the assessment scope over time, and to assess external code. The main function of the **Risk Assessment for Cyber-physical Interconnected Infrastructures** (MRA) is the identification and modelling of the cyber-physical interconnections of infrastructure assets. Firstly, a user inserts a threat scenario, which is the initiating point for an impact assessment accounting for cascading effects within and between inter-connected infrastructures. MRA follows the ISO 27005 approach, and its novelty lies on the decomposition of both the likelihood and consequences elements of risk. The tool is customizable with respect to the impacts and their importance to the network operation. This is a tool for modelling and visualization of risks and cascade effects and fits CI, cascade effects, and it comes from a UE project.

2.1.25 SPHINX Project

SPHINX³⁹ project (SU-TDS-02-2018) aims to introduce a health tailored Universal Cyber Security Toolkit, thus enhancing the cyber protection of the Health and Care IT Ecosystem and ensuring patients' data privacy and integrity. SPHINX aims to introduce a Universal Cyber Security Toolkit, thus enhancing the cyber protection

³⁹ <https://sphinx-project.eu/>

of Health IT Ecosystem and ensuring the patient data privacy and integrity. It will also provide an automated zero-touch device and service verification toolkit that will be easily adapted or embedded on existing, medical, clinical or health available infrastructures.

SPHINX brings a Universal **Cyber Security Toolkit** for the Health and Care Domain that enhances the cyber protection of the healthcare IT ecosystem and ensures the patients' data privacy and integrity. The SPHINX toolkit offers an embedded, smart and robust security awareness layer, able to identify modern and advance cyber threats, enhanced with a personalised data security management tool. This is a suite of tools, targeted for protecting the healthcare sector infrastructures. Some of the tools, work for vulnerability or attack prevention and detection while other tools take these events as inputs to raise combined alerts or react to the threat. This is an integrated set of tools for securing healthcare infrastructure and data. The SPHINX suite is an integrated and certified set of tools, covering a wide range of scenarios to secure a hospital.

- **Decision Support System (DSS):** Decision support system for healthcare. Integrated into SPHINX suite. This tool aims to predict attacks by using ML but also mitigate in real time some attacks onto the healthcare infrastructure. Detection of insights before an attack has been successfully performed and reactive execution of countermeasures to mitigate. The Decision Support System is an engine developed for the SPHINX Toolkit based on Docker framework making it suitable for cloud and on-premise installations. The DSS has two Functionalities. The Proactive functionality uses the network traffic to predict an upcoming cyber-attack and notifies the user of the attack and suggests a fast reaction like blocking the attacker's IP address. To achieve this, the solution relies on the advances of Machine Learning Algorithms. The Active functionality suggests a targeted response plan based on attack and the combination of the information from other components.
- **Real-time Cyber Risk Assessment (RCRA):** The Real-time Cyber Risk assessment (RCRA), assesses the risk of cyber-security incidents and indication of probable consequences, taking information from vulnerability reports, logs and data from other SPHINX components, and format them into common identifiers and descriptions from security knowledge databases (VCDB, MITRE or NVD). Periodic risk estimation of a healthcare infrastructure. Risk analyzer from inputs of other security tools in the SPHINX suite.
- **Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (VAaaS):** The Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (VAaaS) is a system of automatic assessment of vulnerabilities inside a network. It offers seamless assessment for all existing and newly introduced network entities against all known security vulnerabilities, certifies them through a Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS), classifies them according to the cyber-threat they introduce, and finally assigns them to a connectivity-appropriate VLAN.
- **Analytics Engine:** SPHINX Analytics Engine is based on Docker framework making it suitable for cloud and on-premise installations. The Analytics engine provides the ability to monitor how many attacks identified and the attack events based on historical data for a time interval. It Provides bar plots used for the visualization of the identified event and provides all the required information to address future events. The information can be used from other cybersecurity services and end-users to detect suspicious or malicious cyber activities, identify their type and do appropriate courses of action that can be used to stop the detected attacks and vulnerabilities.
- **Blockchain-based Threat Registry Platform (BBTR):** The BBTR is a tool that provides a shared registry of threats by using an Hyperledger Fabric blockchain network. It also provides a listener tool that enables the final users to subscribe to real-time events from the blockchain, allowing them to know when a new threat has been submitted. A user-friendly frontend has also been developed so final users can use a web interface to interact with the BBTR, for purposes such as auditability among others.
- **Service Integration middleware:** Software solution in the form of an integration middleware for bridging third parties' software components, each focused on different functions of a cybersecurity toolbox.
- **Machine Learning-empowered Intrusion Detection using Honeypot's data (MLID):** The Automated Intrusion detection solution transforms multi-dimensional network traffic data generated from honeypots into an actionable and easy-to-understand indicator for security experts. To achieve this, the solution relies on state-of-the-art data mining algorithms and the latest advances in machine learning and deep learning networks.

- **Artificial Intelligence Honeypots:** AI Honeypots of SPHINX are realised both as virtual and hardware appliances. The virtual one is based on docker framework making it suitable for both cloud and on-premise installations; the hardware one mainly suited for on-premise installations comes in two flavours, the first one based on a low-cost Advanced RISC Machine (ARM) system – Quad-core Cortex-A7 central processing unit (CPU) – that is able to support lightweight detection algorithms whereas the second one is capable of operating as a honeypot and a router system, with the capability of handling computing-intensive algorithms without a noticeable delay for the attacker. To achieve this, the system utilises programmable logic in the form of a compact low power field-programmable gate array (FPGA) module. SPHINX AI Honeypots are to be part of an organisation's cyber defence arsenal aiming to detect manifested cyber-attacks as early as possible by luring the adversaries to attack them instead of the real production IT systems. In this direction, the honeypots host vulnerable services that may be considered targets from an adversary.
- **Cybersecurity Knowledge Base (KB):** Cybersecurity Knowledge Base (KB) repository plays a key role in collaborative threat analysis, automated threat exchange and automated detection and response. In this direction, it stores and offers cyber threat intelligence (CTI) information (e.g. attack patterns, vulnerabilities, threat indicators, etc) using the OASIS STIX (Structured Threat Information Expression) language. The KB information can be used from other cybersecurity services, such as threat detection engines, Honeypots, Decision Support systems to detect suspicious or malicious cyber activities, identify their type and recommend appropriate courses of action that can be used to address the detected attacks and vulnerabilities. Besides enabling its users to register new attack patterns and vulnerabilities, the KB additionally collects threat intelligence knowledge from third-party threat intelligence share repositories such as NIST's National Vulnerability Database and MITRE's Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification towards capturing the latest screenshot of the continuous evolving cybersecurity threat landscape.
- **API for Third Parties (S-API):** The SPHINX API for Third Parties is an innovation based on a programmatic interface that enables developers of medical devices or specialised clinical software to access the available SPHINX services to validate whether their devices, systems or applications are compatible with the high cybersecurity levels upheld by the SPHINX System, thus receiving a SPHINX certification. The assets that present cybersecurity vulnerabilities receive a detailed report identifying the changes required to be implemented so that those devices, systems or applications may obtain the SPHINX certification and become a trusted asset.
- **Homomorphic Encryption (HE):** The Homomorphic Encryption Tool is in the form of computation time, particularly the time taken for data anonymization and the time taken for search in the encrypted database. It also logs the time taken for the decryption process.
- **Security Protocol Analysis (SPA):** The SPA allows researchers to define and test security protocols. It provides an expressive formal language for specifying security protocols and their properties along with automatic analysis techniques.
- **Forensic Data Collection Engine (FDCE):** The FDCE component supports the processing and storage of data gathered from various sources in a unified structure in order to discover the relationships between devices and the evidence and produce a timeline of the incident, including a map of affected devices and a set of a meaningful chain of evidence (linked evidence).
- **Attack and Behaviour Simulators (ABS):** The ABS component is a framework capable of simulating user behaviour inside a network through automated procedures and user profiling procedures based on real network data. Also, it comes with a series of virtual machine-based environments capable of reproducing various attack and malicious behaviour patterns.
- **Anomaly Detection (AD):** Anomaly Detection component is based on both machine learning algorithms and statistics-based algorithms. The AD thus performs a fast and efficient analysis of packets in a network and detects unknown attacks, in part due to the rapid development of malware.
- **Interactive Dashboards (ID):** Interactive Dashboards (ID) is a component that centralizes and converts data (web traffic, alerts) obtained from other SPHINX components in different types of graphical representations (tables, graphs, diagrams and custom plugins) to offer IT staff a faster and more compact interpretation of the network system. ID represents the entry point for users to the SPHINX system

- **Data Traffic Monitoring (DTM)** is a SPHINX component responsible for threat identification by monitoring the network traffic and applying signature-based detection analysis. It monitors all the packets traversing the network and compares them against a database of attack signatures or attributes of known malicious threats. Data Traffic Monitoring (DTM) is an intrusion detection system (IDS)
- **Security Information and Event Management (SIEM)**: The SIEM tool plays a key role in real-time threats detection by monitoring logs, flows and events of applications, networks, operational systems, devices and many other data sources. The SIEM Agent is responsible for monitoring any asset output and sending it to SIEM ingestor component that parses the raw data into custom source types before being stored in the central log repository. The SIEM real-time monitoring component brings pre-built use cases based on the MITRE's knowledge base attacks tactics and is responsible to raise alerts when malicious activity is identified. SIEM has a user-friendly interface that enables use cases, dashboards and schedulers configuration. To facilitate threat hunting and event correlation the SIEM UI still has a search tool where all the central log repositories can be queried in a query language of the security operator's choice.

2.1.26 CORE Project

CORE⁴⁰ – Consistently Optimised Resilient Secure Global Supply-Chains project, in the context of Optimisation for resilient and secure supply chains, has demonstrated how a powerful and innovative Consistently Optimised RESilient ecosystem implementation, integrating interoperability, security, resilience and real-time optimisation can produce cost effective, fast and robust solutions that will guarantee the efficient and secure transit of goods through the worldwide Global Supply Chain system. CORE will show how protecting and securing the Global Supply Chain, and reducing its vulnerability to disruption (whether caused by natural disasters, terrorism or other forms of undesirable or illegal activity), can be done while guaranteeing the promotion of a timely and efficient flow of legitimate commerce through the European Union (EU) and other nations around the world. CORE will demonstrate that this can be done while at the same time offering tangible benefits to involved stakeholders (transaction, transport, regulatory and financial operators), thus facilitating its adoption by commercial entities.

In the context of the project, an **attack graph** approach has been developed to identify events of interest in a network of CIs and propagate the relevant information and notifications to all related CIs. A federated network of CIs that combines a Kafka backbone for Pub/Sub event/message handling together with a Neo4J implementation where a Knowledge Graph provides the knowledge about CI interrelations. AI algorithms are run on top of these and fed with information to identify events of interest in real-time and take action to solve potential issues. This approach allows for predicting potential cascade effects of events in a network of CIs (or a network of CI networks). Can be used in environments with uncertainty about events.

Another result is the **CORE Ecosystem**, a 'system-of-systems' federation of supply chains. The CORE Ecosystem Architecture is a structure of inter-related 'building blocks' that can be used by every supply chain to build systems for risk awareness, risk management, optimisation and stakeholder collaborations. The CORE Ecosystem provides the foundation to link, configure and extend diverse technical solutions for supply chain partners, providing the basis for supply chains to establish data pipelines.

2.1.27 INSPECTr Project

INSPECTr⁴¹ – Intelligence Network & Secure Platform for Evidence Correlation and Transfer project principal objective will be to develop a shared intelligent platform and a novel process for gathering, analysing, prioritising and presenting key data to help in the prediction, detection and management of crime in support of multiple agencies at local, national and international level.

In the context of the project, **Knowledge Graphs** for storing criminal cases and evidence have been developed. The solution provides a framework for police officers to store criminal cases and all related information/evidence, and to retrieve this information upon request together with any potential relations to other cases and information in the database. The purpose of the system is to ingest information and evidence from criminal cases and store it in a Knowledge Graph. When an officer creates a new case in the system and

⁴⁰ <http://www.coreproject.eu/>

⁴¹ <https://inspectr-project.eu/>

provides some information and evidence, they can visualise how the current case and its evidence may be related to other cases and their information/evidence. Store and visualise evidence and their interrelations, Ability to find related cases to the one an inspector is working on and to understand how evidence may be related.

2.1.28 SELIS Project

SELIS⁴² – Towards a Shared European Logistics Intelligent Information Space, is aimed at delivering a ‘platform for pan-European logistics applications’ by:

- Embracing a wide spectrum of logistics perspectives and creating a unifying operational and strategic business innovation agenda for pan European Green Logistics.
- Establishing an exceptionally strong consortium of logistics stakeholders and ICT providers, that can leverage EU IP from over 40 projects so as to create proof of concept Common Communication and navigation platforms for pan-European logistics applications deployed in 8 living labs representing the principal logistics communities.
- Establishing a research and innovation environment using the living labs to provide data than can be used for discovery of new insights that will enable continuous value creation supporting the large scale adoption of SELIS.

In the context of SELIS project, a **Knowledge Graph based metamodel** for supply/logistics chains based on open standards has been developed. work in this project is involved with the identification of supply/logistics chains and entities in current chains, and the transformation of these to support particular European Green Logistics Strategies (7 identified within the SELIS project). This is done via analysing the chains in the LLs of the project, and then deriving a meta model for Shared Knowledge Graphs which is universal and based on open standards. INLE are also involved in the related deliverable and there is direct transfer of knowledge from this project especially in the area of Knowledge Graph creation and deployment. The metamodel can abstract various supply/logistics chain models and situations. It provides core graph-based representation features and functions e.g. to match different shipping stages that are spatially and/or temporally similar, and also a unified representation for handling events of interest. Provides a unified way of generating and searching T&L graph-based models (meta model) which can abstract various logistics or supply chain situations and models. The solution can be deployed via the Cloud as part of a PaaS solution using e.g. Heroku or other PaaS solutions that support python-based applications.

2.1.29 CHARIOT Project

CHARIOT⁴³ – Cognitive Heterogeneous Architecture for Industrial IoT, provides a methodology and cognitive computing platform for a unified approach towards privacy, security and safety of IoT systems.

The project will advance state of the art by providing a design method and cognitive computing platform supporting a unified approach towards Privacy, Security and Safety (PSS) of IoT Systems, that places devices and hardware at the root of trust, in turn contributing to high security and integrity of industrial IoT. More specifically, for each of the PSS ‘imperatives’, a highly innovative approach is proposed as follows:

- A Privacy and Security Protection method building on concepts from state-of-the-art Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) technologies, to enable the coupling of a pre-programmed private key deployed to IoT devices with a corresponding private key on Blockchain system for the purposes of affirming and approving valid transactions.
- A Blockchain ledger in which categories of IoT physical, operational and functional changes are both recorded and affirmed/approved through a combination of coupling a cognitive engine and private key hashing between the cognitive engine and IoT devices to authorise change and, likewise, invalidating any and all other changes whether malicious or otherwise. Such a ledger provides a compelling journal and audit log from which, through machine learning, past patterns can be used as a basis to highlight present anomalies and inconsistencies and, in turn, halting execution in situations where transactions and workflows deviate from established patterns of behaviour.

⁴² <https://selisproject.eu/>

⁴³ <https://www.chariotproject.eu/>

- A fog-based decentralised infrastructure for Firmware and Operational Security integrity checking that leverages a Blockchain ledger to enhance physical, operational and functional security of IoT systems, such as actuation, deactivation, transactions of all types including business process workflows and their associated business logic.
- An accompanying IoT Safety Supervision Engine providing a novel solution to the challenges of securing IoT data, devices and functionality for new and existing industry-specific safety critical systems.
- A Cognitive System and Method with accompanying supervision, analytics and prediction models that encapsulates these latter capabilities, with the end goal of high fidelity security and integrity of Industrial IoT.
- New methods and tools for static code analysis of IoT devices, resulting in more efficient secure and safer IoT software development and V&V.

CHARIOT will advance state of the art by providing a design method and cognitive computing platform supporting a unified approach towards Privacy, Security and Safety (PSS) of IoT Systems, that places devices and hardware at the root of trust, in turn contributing to high security and integrity of industrial IoT. More specifically, CHARIOT will develop the following:

- Public Key Infrastructure to enable coupling of a pre-programmed private key deployed to IoT devices with a corresponding private key on Blockchain
- A Block-chain ledger in which IoT's physical, operational and functional changes are both recorded and affirmed/approved
- A fog-based decentralized infrastructure for Firmware Security integrity checking
- IoT Safety Supervision Engine for securing IoT data, devices and functionality in new and existing industry-specific safety critical systems.
- A Cognitive System and Method with accompanying supervision, analytics and prediction models
- New methods and tools for static code analysis of IoT devices

Specifically, **Privacy-by-design methods & security engines** have been developed. VLTN in CHARIOT has developed the reference architecture and systems. In short, based on a comprehensive understanding of IoT vulnerabilities and risks, VLTN has developed a unified platform for proactive IoT sensor management using Blockchain techniques among others. This includes several topics such as end-to-end-security, encryption-by-design and trust/accountability. These engines protect communications in IoT data exchanges and identify trusted hardware to send data to and allow end-to-end security in IoT sensory data acquisition and communication across all levels (Cloud, Fog, Edge).

3 Conclusions

In conclusion, the establishment of a shared lexicon plays a crucial role in facilitating the exchange of information and expertise. The creation of a unified risk taxonomy builds upon existing frameworks, merging them to ensure comprehensive coverage of risk terminology. Emphasizing the identification of threats is integral to a thorough risk analysis process. Rather than starting from scratch, a pragmatic approach involves developing the threat taxonomy for Critical Infrastructures (CIs) based on the threats gathered from literature and various sources.

Our exploration extends beyond mere taxonomy, delving into current literature and EU-funded security projects. This review aims to understand existing attempts to categorize Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) measures, products, and systems. The categorization of security products and systems varies based on technology and contextual usage, with considerations for responses to specific threats and overarching concerns. Additionally, classifications related to crisis management phases offer valuable insights. The expanded analysis of previous EU projects and the in-depth examination of specific CIP solutions further enrich our understanding of this critical domain.

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